

EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Final protocol)

Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 10109505

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Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments (EPIC-WE)
Year: 2025
Read more about EPIC-WE: <https://epic-we.eu>

Technical References

Deliverable title	Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Final protocol)
Document type	Report
Dissemination level 1	PU (Public)
Work package	WP3 – Ecosystems, Interventions and Methods
Task	T3.2
Lead beneficiary	AU – Aarhus University
Contributing beneficiaries	NISV; MEET; CBC
Authors	Rikke Toft Nørgård & Kim Holflod, Aarhus University, Danish School of Education, Denmark (AU)
Due date of deliverable	30.11.2024
Actual submission date	28.02.2025
Reviewed by	María Ruigómez Eraso (KEA); Kasper Marius Nørmark (AROS); Conceição Costa (UL); Regitze Mai Møller (AAKS); Nélío Codices (BS); Belit Ayaydin (CBC); René van Engelenburg (DM)

Document History

Version	Date	Status
V1	04.12.2024	Initial shared incomplete draft
V2	18.02.2025	First revised version following review by Coordinator
V3	26.02.2025	Second revised version following review by WP3; T3.2 Task Participants
V4	27.02.2025	Final revised version following review by Executive Board and Coordinator
V5	28.02.2025	Submitted final version

Colophon

1st Edition 2025

Grant Agreement ID: 101095058

Project DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15346071

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This publication can be viewed online and downloaded as pdf.

Please visit www.epic-we.eu

How to cite this report:

Nørgård, R. T. & Holfod, K. (2025). D3.3 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Final protocol). EPIC-WE Horizon Europe Project. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15346071

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 10109505. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

0. Executive Summary

This report, D3.2 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit – EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools, represents the final version of Protocol 2 within the EPIC-WE project (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments). The D3.2 Protocol 2 is a direct extension of the initial D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) and should as such be read together. The D3.2 Protocol 2 further refines and extends the Cultural Game Jam (CGJ) Kit created based on the D3.1 Protocol 2 through integrating the empirical insights, design interventions, publications and deliverables produced from the cross-sector research and innovation activities carried out in the EPIC-WE project during 2024-2025. The Protocol 2 outlines key methodologies, structural refinements, and practical applications to advance the role of cultural game jams in fostering cultural heritage engagement, game-making as culture-making, and youth empowerment.

Overview of D3.1 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit

The D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) introduced and described the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam (CGJ) Kit as a structured framework and methodology for organising and running cultural game jams to create games through/for culture across diverse European sites and contexts. The CGJ Kit includes:

The EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model (E-P-I-C):

A four-phase approach (Experience, Play, Imagine, Create) designed to scaffold cultural engagement, empowerment, and citizenship through game-making.

EPIC-WE Dimensions (W-E Dimensions):

The World and Empowerment dimensions, ensuring engagement with cultural worlds and environments and empowered participation in cultural heritage.

EPIC-WE 4 Core Categories:

The core categories of Culture, Values, Citizenship, and Games position Cultural Game Jams as a format for exploring and practising cultural heritage, EU values, cultural citizenship, identity, and belonging.

EPIC-WE Phase Transition Tools:

The four transition tools Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, and Log & Pitch, developed to facilitate participants' transition from one phase to the next in the cultural game jam towards the creation and presentation of their games through/for culture.

Extensions and Refinements of the CGJ Kit in D3.2 Protocol 2

While preserving the above elements of the CGJ Kit, the D3.2 Protocol 2 significantly extends the CGJ Kit through incorporating empirical data from the first six CGJs (CGJ 1-6) and aligning the methodology with broader sectoral, local, and glocal dimensions. Key extensions include:

1 Integration of Local, Glocal, and Sector Dimensions:

The refined Protocol 2 emphasises contextual adaptability, ensuring that cultural game jams effectively engage with specific cultural heritage sites, needs, values, and themes.

2 Fundamental Principles for Cultural Game Jams:

The refined Protocol 2 emphasises seven fundamental principles that underpin and guide the design and execution of CGJs:

- a. **CGJ Principle 1:** Three ways to run Cultural Game Jams
- b. **CGJ Principle 2:** Aimed at cultural participation, co-creation, and empowerment
- c. **CGJ Principle 3:** Foster cultural curiosity and creativity
- d. **CGJ Principle 4:** Cultivate an “epic we” through Cultural Game Jams
- e. **CGJ Principle 5:** Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making
- f. **CGJ Principle 6:** Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation
- g. **CGJ Principle 7:** Create games through and for culture and cultural transformation

3 Key Insights from Design-Based Research Interventions (CGJ 1-6):

Cross-hub thematic analyses of all empirical data, all Cultural Game Jam events, and all 40+ games through/for culture created by youth, serve as the research foundation of the refinement and extension of Protocol 2 and the CGJ Kit. This research foundation provided critical insights and core recommendations for the extension of Protocol 2 and defined extensions of the CGJ Kit:

a. Empowered Participation: Youth involvement in planning, executing, and evaluating CGJs enhances engagement and co-ownership of cultural heritage, citizenship, and values.

b. Sector Integration: Stronger collaboration between CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and YCs fosters transformative partnerships and meeting in the middle to organise and run cultural game jams together in QH Cultural Hubs.

c. Iterative Adaptation: The CGJ Kit contains flexibility to accommodate different cultural contexts, skill levels, and institutional frameworks.

d. Facilitation Strategies: Effective facilitation balances structured guidance with participant-driven creativity, ensuring both accessibility and depth of engagement.

e. Cultural Empowerment: The CGJ Kit contains two application methods focusing on cultural heritage and cultural/societal themes respectively to ensure cultural heritage engagement and empowerment in culture.

4 Three Distinct Compositions of the CGJ Kit:

The D3.2 Protocol 2 extends the CGJ Kit with the possibility of running CGJs with three different compositions of the CGJ Kit:

a. Focused CGJ Kit: A standardised framework ensuring consistency and quality across CGJs.

b. Flexible CGJ Kit: Allows local adaptation through curated method selection while maintaining structural integrity.

c. Freeform CGJ Kit: Grants entire creative autonomy to participants, enabling them to shape their own cultural game-making journey.

5

Games through Culture and Games for Culture:

The D3.2 Protocol 2 significantly extends the CGJ Kit with its division of the CGJ Kit into two main application methods focusing on utilising cultural heritage as creative game-making material and game-making directed at cultural/societal themes or issues through games respectively:

- a. **CGJ Kit for Games through Culture:** Using cultural heritage as material for game-making, fostering engagement with historical narratives and artifacts.
- b. **CGJ Kit for Games for Culture:** Creating games that address societal values, citizenship, and cultural transformation.

6

Recommendations for Future Research and Implementation:

To ensure impact and scalability of CGJs, the following recommendations are proposed:

- a. **Strengthen Youth Participation in CGJ Planning and Facilitation:** Expand the role of youth in decision-making. Ensure youth-led facilitation models are embedded within the CGJ process.
- b. **Enhance Accessibility and Inclusivity:** Provide preparatory materials and mentorship tailored to different experience levels and participant needs.
- c. **Advance Cultural Heritage Integration:** Emphasise game-making processes and methodologies that deepen cultural engagement and empowerment.
- d. **Expand Cross-Sector Collaboration:** Strengthen partnerships between CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and YCs to facilitate transformative partnerships, close collaboration, and enhanced value and sustainability in solutions.

The D3.2 Protocol 2 marks a significant advancement in developing the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam methodology. By extending the CGJ Kit with refined frameworks, empirical validation, and practical recommendations, this report lays the foundation for broader implementation across cultural and educational ecosystems. The project's commitment to cultural participation, co-creation, and empowered game-making ensures that CGJs evolve as innovative platforms for cultural heritage engagement, youth empowerment, and creative expression across Europe.

Introduction

01

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The EPIC-WE project: Cultural Game Jams

The EPIC-WE project (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments, 2023-2026) presents with this report the D3.2 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit, EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools, a report laying the foundation for the Cultural Game Jam Kit (CGJ Kit) that will be developed at the backdrop of the report to support game-making as a form of culture-making. The final D3.2 Protocol 2 report builds upon previous iterations and conceptual models by integrating extensive empirical research, iterative design interventions, and cross-sector collaborations. It also documents the evolution of the CGJ Kit from its initial proof-of-concept to its final version published on the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#) at the end of the project (2026).

The D3.2 Protocol 2 report is organised into several key sections that collectively provide a comprehensive account of the project's achievements, innovations, and future directions. In what follows, we outline the report's structure, underscore its key contributions, and situate the work within the broader context of cultural heritage, youth empowerment and citizenship, and innovative game-making and culture-making practices.

At the heart of the EPIC-WE project lies a commitment to reimagine cultural participation, identity, belonging, and empowerment by leveraging game-making as a medium for cultural expression and transformation. Traditional approaches to cultural heritage are reinterpreted here through the dynamic, co-creative processes of Cultural Game Jams and youth developing games through/for culture. The project challenges conventional boundaries between cultural heritage preservation and cultural heritage innovation and transformation by engaging young citizens, cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and higher education institutions in a collaborative process. The CGJ Kit, as presented in [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) and further described in this report, provides a tangible framework and methodology that guides participants through the CGJ process. The CGJ contains four E-P-I-C phases: Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. Each phase is designed to foster an immersive engagement with cultural heritage narratives, values, and themes. At the same time, the CGJ Kit developed on the basis of the Protocol 2 ensure that the result of a CGJ adheres to the EPIC-WE project's research and innovation into cultural heritage, cultural game jams, youth empowerment, and games through/for culture.

Key Contributions of the Report

The D3.2 Protocol 2 report contributes significantly to both theoretical and practical understandings of cultural game jams. It refines and extends the initial [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) developed in D3.1 by:

Integrating Local, Glocal, and Sector Dimensions

The Protocol 2 is extended in D3.2 by incorporating multiple dimensions, enhancing the applicability of CGJs across diverse European contexts. The report outlines a robust and adaptable framework by embedding local sensitivities, global–local (glocal) perspectives, and specific sector dimensions (involving cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth citizens).

Defining Fundamental Principles for Cultural Game Jams

The report extrapolates seven fundamental principles underpinning and guiding CGJa by synthesising research results and empirical insights gathered from the first six CGJs carried out in 2024. This major contribution, which contains the fundamental principles for CGJs- ranging from the balanced integration of structure and flexibility to the emphasis on value-and culture-sensitive game-making - provides a conceptual foundation that guides current implementations and informs future iterations of CGJs.

Articulating Three Distinct CGJ Kit Compositions

The report significantly contributes by detailing three general compositions within the CGJ Kit: Focused, Flexible, and Freeform CGJs. Each composition addresses specific challenges and opportunities encountered in different cultural contexts and participant constellations. This differentiation underscores the report’s commitment to cultural and contextual sensitivity and participant empowerment, ensuring that both novice and experienced game-makers can find a suitable and engaging process across different sites and contexts.

Empirical Validation through Design-Based Research

Drawing on data collected from interventions in Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos, the report provides an in-depth analysis of the CGJ Kit’s iterative development. Incorporating participant, facilitator, and advisory board feedback has enabled the team to identify best practices, address logistical challenges, and optimise the balance between guided structure and creative freedom. These empirical insights validate the kit’s potential as a replicable framework and methodology for cultural innovation and transformation across diverse European settings.

Bridging Game-Making and Culture-Making:

The report challenges traditional views of cultural heritage and creative production by positioning game-making as a form of culture-making. It demonstrates how games can serve as interactive, transformative cultural experiences for reimagining cultural heritage and fostering cultural dialogue. This dual focus on games through culture and games for culture positions the extended CGJ Kit as a catalyst for cultural engagement, empowering youth to actively contribute to the evolving cultural heritage landscape.

Overview of the Report's Structure

The D3.2 Protocol 2 (final) is structured into several interconnected sections, each building upon the preceding ones to form a coherent narrative of the development and implementation of CGJs and the CGJ Kit. The main sections are outlined below:

1. Introduction

The introductory section, as presented here, situates the report within the context of the EPIC-WE project. It delineates the conceptual underpinnings of cultural game jams and explains the rationale for extending and refining the initial CGJ Kit. The introduction also outlines the report's key contributions and provides a roadmap for the following sections.

2. Cultural Game Jam Kit

This central section delves into the further evolution of the CGJ Kit that the D3.2 Protocol 2 delineates. It begins with a summary of the initial CGJ Kit tested in the first round of interventions (CGJ 1-6), highlighting insights and implications from empirical analyses. Subsequent subsections address the integration of sector, local, and glocal dimensions and an in-depth overview of the kit's elements. The section concludes with a detailed presentation of the fundamental principles that should underpin and guide all cultural game jams, ensuring alignment with the research and innovation results of the EPIC-WE initiative.

3. The Focused, Flexible, and Freeform CGJ Kit

Recognising the diversity of cultural contexts and varied participant needs, this section introduces three variants of the CGJ Kit.

- o **The Focused CGJ Kit** is presented as the project's standard model that all CGJs incorporate. It is designed to provide a clear, structured CGJ process for game-making with set methods and tools that ensure consistency and quality.

- o **The Flexible CGJ Kit** allows local cultural hubs to tailor the core model by incorporating additional methods and role cards that reflect local cultural themes, emphases, specificities, and participant backgrounds, striking a balance between guidance and adaptability.

- o **The Freeform CGJ Kit** offers maximum creative freedom, enabling participants to select methods based on their individual interests and team dynamics from the complete CGJ Kit.

4. Game-Making as Culture-Making

This section articulates the EPIC-WE approach that underlies Cultural Game Jams and Games through/for culture: positioning game-making as culture-making. It explores the conceptual shift from traditional cultural heritage practices to a dynamic model where game-making is employed as a cultural innovation and transformation tool. This section demonstrates how cultural game jams can be organised and run – using the CGJ Kit – as a way to foster empowered participation in culture and as cultural engagement through the creation of games through/for culture.

5. The Heritage-Focused and Citizenship-Focused Cultural Game Jam Kits

Recognising that cultural game jams can address distinct aspects of cultural engagement, the report divides the CGJ Kit into two primary domains:

- o **The Games through Culture CGJ Kit** emphasises using cultural heritage as the foundation for game-making. This approach supports the imagination, interpretation and transformation of cultural heritage by enabling participants to explore and experiment with cultural heritage as game-making material.

- o **The Games for Culture CGJ Kit** focuses on addressing broader cultural or societal themes and issues, positioning game-making as a medium for cultural transformation and civic engagement.

6. Development and Evaluation of the CGJ Kit

The final substantive section details the process of implementing and assessing the CGJ Kit towards its redesign on the basis of the D3.2 Protocol 2 found here. It synthesises findings from the first round of Design-Based Research interventions (CGJ 1-6) and outlines the refinements and extensions made in response to participant feedback and facilitator insights.

7. Conclusion

The report concludes by reflecting on the overall achievements of CGJs and the CGJ Kit and the transformative potential of cultural game jams. It summarises the key insights and contributions of the report, reiterating the importance of fostering empowered participation and cultural innovation through game-making. The concluding chapter also outlines recommendations for future research and practical implementations, ensuring that the lessons learned can be applied to subsequent European projects and initiatives.

The D3.2 Protocol 2 (final) represents a concrete step toward reimagining cultural heritage and citizenship in a rapidly evolving cultural and social landscape. By bridging the gap between theoretical insights and practical application, the protocol provides cultural institutions, academics, creative industry professionals, and youth with a robust CGJ Kit that can be adapted to a variety of settings and challenges. The emphasis on participatory cultural- and value-sensitive design and QH co-creation reflects a broader shift toward democratising cultural heritage, ensuring that youth are engaged, not only consumers, but as active co-creators and equal partners to the cultural narrative.

Moreover, integrating multiple dimensions – local, glocal, and sector-specific – illustrates the project's commitment to contextual sensitivity. Recognising that cultural heritage is experienced differently across regions and communities, the report advocates for a flexible approach that respects and harnesses these variations. Whether through the fixed structure of the Focused CGJ Kit, the adaptable framework of the Flexible CGJ Kit, or the creative autonomy afforded by the Freeform CGJ Kit, the EPIC-WE project points in new directions for how cultural game jams can be designed and executed, how game-making as culture-making can be practiced, and how youth can create their own games through/for culture, in a way that is both empowering and innovative.

The protocol validates the CGJ Kit's usefulness and provides a framework for its next iteration by systematically analysing the Design-Based Research interventions (CGJ 1-6) across multiple QH Cultural Hubs.

1.2. Developing the EPIC-WE D3.2 Protocol 2

Protocol 2 is developed through concepts, theories, and approaches from Protocol 1, e.g., the quadruple helix innovation ecosystem and the cultural hubs, emphasising how they become vital elements of designing, facilitating, and reflecting on CGJs. Through T4.3 the first round of design interventions with CGJs were analysed, examining both the local games and game prototypes created, the CGJs as local events, and broader and permeative analyses across the diverse and thick empirical material. These analyses provided the foundation for continued studies in T2.4, emphasising the glocal elements and perspectives.

Overall, the development of D3.2 Protocol 2 draws from substantial experiences and analyses of CGJ 1-6 (as well as one pilot intervention), along with the combined effort of WP2, WP3, and WP4. WP2 provides the state-of-the-art and theoretical grounding for the design of ecosystems, methods, and approaches in WP3, which is tested and analysed locally in WP4 and analysed glocally in WP2. Within the project's iterative DBR approach, glocal interventions (WP4) then commence as part of the second round of interventions.

1.3. Summary of the D3.1 Protocol 2

The Protocol 2 serves as a foundational resource for developing the CGJ Kit and executing Cultural Game Jams.

The D3.1 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit (2024) introduced the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam (CGJ) Kit and described the processes, phases, methods, and tools necessary for executing cultural game jams in local European sites.

Overall, the D3.1 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit substantiates and details the initial EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit containing:

A. EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model:

A four-step model presenting the Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create (E-P-I-C) phases, each guiding participants through game-making as a cultural process.

B. EPIC-WE Dimensions:

the World and Empowerment (W-E) Dimensions, emphasising cultural heritage engagement and youth empowerment.

C. EPIC-WE Transition Tools:

four Transition Tools to help CGJ participants transition between the phases of the CGJ: for Experience the Ideation Wheel, for Play the Expert Council, for Imagine the Playtest, and for Create the Log & Pitch, scaffolding structured game design.

D. EPIC-WE Core Categories:

the Core Categories for Cultural Game Jams were defined: Culture, Games, Values, and Citizenship, to support and promote Games *through/for* Culture and position game-making as a new form of culture-making.

The final D3.2 Protocol 2 extends the CGJ Kit from the initial D3.1 Protocol 2 by:

1. Adding **local, glocal, and sector dimensions** to the CGJ Kit enhances local-glocal use and contextual sensitivity.

2. Defining the **fundamental principles** for Cultural Game Jams to ensure understanding of what distinguishes and characterises the format.

3. Organising the CGJ Kit into a **focused, flexible, and freeform format** to enable adaptability to concrete and different events and activities formats.

4. Dividing the CGJ Kit into a **Games through Culture Kit** and a **Games for Culture Kit** will target the two main domains of the CGJ Kit: Cultural heritage and citizenship.

The above extensions are further detailed in this D3.2 Protocol 2 (final) to build upon and refine the CGJ Kit developed in D3.1 Protocol 2 (initial). The extensions are created through the project's design, execution, and evaluation of Design-Based Research interventions, Cultural Game Jam 1-6, utilisation of the CGJ Kit, and research outcomes resulting from the analysis of all CGJ events and the 40+ created games through/for culture made by youth in them. The foundation of this report can be found on the [EPIC-WE Project Website](#) with its deliverables and publications and on the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#) with its games through/for culture and capacity building series.

In more detail, the initial D3.1 Protocol 2 developed, described, and delivered:

A. EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Phases

Each phase of the **Cultural Game Jam Process Model** is designed to guide the participants through the structured yet flexible activity of creating games through/for culture.

● Experience Phase

- Focuses on **cultural exploration**, encouraging participants to engage with cultural heritage sites, artifacts, narratives, and values.
- Uses developed game-making and culture-making methods such as **valuestorming**, **love letters**, and **culture safari** to inspire game concepts through/for culture.

● Play Phase:

- Centres on playful experimentation with gameplay ideas, mechanics, aesthetics, and narratives.
- Uses developed methods such as culture collage, 6-8-5 game sketching, and storyboarding.

● Imagine Phase:

- Involves refining and materialising game ideas into tangible prototypes.
- Uses developed methods such as **citizen experience mapping**, **cultural prototyping**, and **game mock-ups**.

● Create Phase:

- Participants produce a playable game for game players to experience culture through games and games for culture.
- Focuses on documentation, final adjustments, and showcasing the games at the concluding CGJ EXPO

B. EPIC-WE Dimensions: World and Empowerment

Two overarching dimensions, World and Empowerment (W-E), run through all phases of the CGJ:

- **World Dimension:**

Focuses on experience of and interaction with cultural gameworlds, storytelling, and values.

- **Empowerment Dimension:**

Encourages youth to engage with culture and cultural heritage through empowered participation, enabling them to become co-creators of games and culture, fostering creativity, agency, and critical engagement.

These dimensions ensure that games developed within CGJs contribute to **cultural awareness, belonging, and engagement**, reinforcing the broader goals of the EPIC-WE initiative.

C. EPIC-WE Transition Tools

To facilitate the smooth transition between phases, the CGJ Kit introduces four **Transition Tools**, one for each phase:

- **Ideation Wheel:**

- Helps participants experience and generate multiple ideas by exploring culture, values, citizenship, and game topics.

- **Expert Council:**

- Provides youth with feedback from experts and professionals in games and culture targeting these intersections. .

- **Playtest:**

- Enables iterative refinement of the game concept by constructing mock-ups or prototypes that enable participants to test and adjust their games through/for culture based on playtesting.

- **Log & Pitch:**

Prepares teams to showcase their game to audiences at the final EXPO and publish it at the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#).

These tools serve as key milestones within the Cultural Game Jam process, helping participants navigate the complexity of designing games through/for culture while focusing on integrating cultural heritage, values and issues.

D. EPIC-WE Core Categories: Culture, Games, Values, and Citizenship

The CGJ Kit and its methods are structured around four core categories, aligning with the Quadruple Helix Model, which integrates perspectives and elements from:

- **Creative Industries (CIs):** Experts in game design, gameplay, and digital media.
- **Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs):** Experts in cultural heritage, narratives, and contexts.
- **Higher Education Institutions (HEIs):** Experts in value-sensitive design, research methodologies, and educational activities.
- **Youth Citizens (YCs):** Bring their lived experiences, creativity, and perspectives to co-create games through/for culture.

These categories ensure that cultural game-making within CGJs is interdisciplinary, inclusive, and reflective of diverse cultural perspectives.

The initial D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) ensures that the **Cultural Game Jam methodology can be adopted, implemented, and executed** across diverse cultural heritage sites, contexts, and themes strengthening its impact and applicability in game-making and culture-making.

1.4. Overview of the D3.2 Protocol 2

This report is structured to comprehensively document the development, implementation, and iterative refinement of the Cultural Game Jam (CGJ) Kit within the EPIC-WE project. It begins with an **Executive Summary**, providing a concise overview of the key findings from the initial design interventions, analyses, and project insights, alongside recommendations from the project. Following this, the **Introduction** outlines the project's objectives, the development of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit, and a detailed summary of Protocols D3.1 and D3.2, establishing the theoretical and methodological foundations for the CGJ kits.

The report subsequently presents the extension of the **Cultural Game Jam Kit** developed in D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#). This section summarises insights from the first round of CGJs, investigating sectoral, local, and "glocal" (global-local) dimensions that shaped the design and adaptation of the CGJ Kit's components. A dedicated segment on the **Focused, Flexible, and Freeform CGJ Kit** presents the difference between the three and highlight the enhanced adaptability of the CGJ Kit to concrete and different events and activities formats adaptability to concrete and different events and activities formats.

Subsequent sections explore the thematic frameworks of **game-making as culture-making**, and divided the CGJ Kit into a **Games through Culture Kit** and a **Games for Culture Kit** to target the two main domains of the CGJ Kit: Young people creating games through their participation in cultural heritage and their use of cultural heritage as game-making material and young people making games for engaging cultural and societal issues and their use of cultural values and citizenship as culture-making participation. These parts also highlight insights from the first six Cultural Game Jams in Hilversum, Aarhus and Óbidos, the revisions made to the CGJ Kit, and how the sectoral, local, and glocal dimensions have informed these.

The report concludes with a chapter on **delivering the CGJ Kit Version 2**. This section synthesises findings from earlier sections and outlines the final iteration of the CGJ Kit, which is ready for broader applications and publication on the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#).

Cultural Game Jam Kit

02

2. CULTURAL GAME JAM KIT

2.1 Summary of CGJ Kit, CGJ 1-6

The CGJ Kit tested and evaluated across the CGJ interventions in Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos has evolved significantly through multiple iterations to facilitate the core objectives of EPIC-WE better:

- Game jamming with cultural heritage, values and cultural/social themes
- Game-making as a new form of culture-making
- Youth creating games through culture and games for culture
- Empowered participation in cultural worlds and environments

In the first version of the CGJ Kit, an ‘EPIC-WE Playbook’ was developed, tested, and evaluated, functioning as a first proof of concept. The EPIC-WE Playbook was developed and piloted at a local game jam hosted by the Aarhus Cultural Hub in December 2023. Here, forty youth participated in a six-hour jam exploring cultural heritage and the EU value of equality. Despite facing challenges such as information overload and issues with the compressed timeframe, all groups succeeded in developing game concepts that used cultural heritage as game-making material and engaged with equality/inequality in different ways, demonstrating the potential of the overall EPIC-WE approach for meaningful cultural heritage participation through game-making.

The second version contained the first fully developed CGJ Kit with its four E-P-I-C phases, W-E dimensions, transition tools, and CGJ methods to target the distinct game-making as culture-making activities going on within each phase. This version was developed, tested, evaluated, and iterated across two full CGJs. The version was released in January 2024, designed as a flexible resource for local Cultural Hubs to adopt, use, and evaluate with reflexivity and context sensitivity. The third version of the CGJ Kit will be created based on the D3.2 Protocol 2 found here, and include redesign based on the DBR intervention analyses, glocal, local and sector dimensions and described CGJ Kit extensions (as presented in this report). This CGJ Kit represents a two-prong approach, resulting in either **games through culture** or **games for culture**, and three different ways of organising the CGJ Kit in the **focused**, **flexible**, or **freeform** mode. This version will be tested glocally during Spring 2025 across all 3 QH Cultural Hubs in Hilversum, Óbidos, and Aarhus and their three final CGJs.

The results of this will lead to the fourth and final version of the CGJ Kit, which will be published on the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#) by the end of the project in early 2026.

2.2 Cultural Game Jams 1-6: Insights and Implications

Preliminary Insights and Recommendations for Cultural Game Jams

In T2.4, the empirical material (interviews, observations, documentation, visual ethnography, collaborative inquiry, etc.) from the first six CGJs was analysed using local thematic analysis across all of the local analyses from T4.3. The analytic write-up identified seven key themes and principles and guiding implications and rationales to strengthen the iteration of the final D3.2, Protocols 2.

1

Promote Collaborative Diversity

Intentionally forming diverse teams with participants of varying skills, backgrounds, and experiences fosters mentorship, innovation, and shared learning. Teams that combined game-making and culture-making expertise, such as high school and university students or experienced and novice contributors, consistently produced innovative and thematically rich games through/for culture. Furthermore, structured opportunities for cross-team collaboration, such as roundtable discussions or thematic challenges, helped build a sense of community and encourage knowledge exchange. Recruitment processes should aim for teams mixing game-making and culture-making expertise (such as design and programming disciplines with arts and culture disciplines) to harness the potential of diversity in CGJs. The transition tools of Expert Council and Playtesting should be utilised to promote interaction and peer feedback, focusing on enhancing cultural creativity and thematic integration.

2

Ensure Accessibility and Inclusivity

Equitable access in CGJs and its materials, methods, tools, CGJ Kit, and facilitated guidance is essential to fostering meaningful and empowered participation. Participants, ranging from high school to seasoned university students (age 15-25), faced technical barriers and confidence gaps. To address this, the CGJ Kit includes easy-to-use methods such as mock-ups, paper prototyping, and more advanced methods to cater to diverse skill levels. Interdisciplinary teams and balancing game-making and culture-making methods can enable less experienced participants to contribute through storytelling, concept art or visual design while learning from their peers. Inclusive facilitation and resource allocation create a more equitable environment, ensuring all participants can contribute effectively and enhance outcomes' overall quality and diversity.

3

Balance Structure with Flexibility

Balancing structured methods with a flexible CGJ Kit to adapt to participants' needs is critical for maintaining creative momentum during cultural game jams. Rigid adherence to predefined and closed processes often disrupted creativity, particularly under time constraints. Facilitators should identify essential activities and methods in the CGJ Kit, while labelling others as adjustable or optional. Enabling facilitators to assess engagement in real-time allows them to modify or skip less critical CGJ Kit elements, fostering a more empowering and organic workflow. Adjustable approaches, such as choosing between the Focused, Flexible, and Freeform CGJ Kit instead of rigid and closed formats, inspire participants to explore ideas freely. Encouraging participants to adjust methods and procedures to their specific game-making and culture-making processes further enhances their ownership of the CGJ process, promoting cultural creativity and sustained focus.

4

Foster CHI and CI Facilitation Synergy

Close collaboration between Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI) and Creative Industries (CI) in QH Cultural Hubs (See D3.2 Protocol 1) and with running Cultural Game Jams, can bridge cultural knowledge with creative execution, ensuring meaningful cultural heritage integration throughout the game jam process. Insights from the Óbidos, Aarhus, and Hilversum hubs revealed varied facilitation styles, each with strengths and challenges. Pairing CHI experts, such as museum curators, with CI professionals, like game designers, enables complementary guidance that balances cultural depth with practical application.

Jointly conducted games through/for culture workshops, Expert Councils, and collaborative challenges can deepen engagement with cultural themes while maintaining creative flexibility. Co-facilitation ensures that participants consistently integrate cultural elements into their games, meeting the dual goals of cultural heritage richness and games through/for culture innovation.

5

Integrate Documentation into the Design Process

The initial [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) contained the Group Game Log 1-4 documentation methods and the Log & Pitch transition tool. Documentation methods should be naturally embedded into the CGJ process to ensure participants can reflect on their game-making and culture-making process without disrupting their workflow. Participants found platforms like Itch.io burdensome for real-time documentation. However, group reflections, visual tools, or collaborative summaries, the CGJ Kit transformed documentation into a valuable resource for ideating and showcasing the created games through/for culture. Presenting documentation as a shared, creative activity allows participants to track their progress better and gain deeper insights into their CGJ process. Facilitators can enhance this by guiding short reflection activities during breaks that can be entered into the Game Logs or help teams summarise key moments, enabling participants to focus on creativity while also capturing their creation of games through/for culture effectively.

6

Meaningful Integration of Cultural Collections and Themes

Game jams can significantly benefit from immersive engagement with cultural heritage, archives, or themes – and vice versa. Participants often faced challenges integrating abstract cultural themes into their game-making process. However, activities like museum tours, hands-on interactions with cultural artefacts, and expert guidance during engagement with specific cultural heritage, themes, or materials provided valuable inspiration. To achieve meaningful cultural heritage integration, the CGJ Kit connects directly game-making and culture-making through its E-P-I-C phases and methods, its W-E Dimensions and its focus on connecting cultural heritage, values, citizenship, game design, mechanics, narratives, and aesthetics. Methods like the ones found in the CGJ Kit that link cultural heritage with game aesthetics or narratives can inspire participants to incorporate themes in more authentic, engaged, and empowering ways. Structured CGJ Kit processes with focused methods and multiple review opportunities through the CGJ Kit transition tools allow teams to receive feedback, ensuring their designs reflect cultural heritage and themes profoundly and creatively.

7

Managing Participant Interaction with Cultural Heritage Sites

Effective use of cultural heritage sites enhances creativity, connection, and commitment to cultural themes but requires careful management to avoid disorientation. Participants appreciated the focused exploration of a specific cultural heritage site for the duration of the CGJ, such as art museums, digital archives, historic cultural cities, or cultural landmarks. A well-organized and focused approach to cultural heritage site as the location for a specific CGJ combines guided activities, such as the Experience and Play methods found in the D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#), with opportunities for self-guided cultural heritage exploration, experimentation, and evaluation. Team-building exercises integrating the cultural heritage site help participants create deeper connections with the site while maintaining a culture-making mindset.

Insights on the application of the CGK Kit in the initial design interventions

The CGJ Kit utilised across the CGJ interventions in Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos evolved significantly across iterations to better support participants' creative processes and thematic integration through the integration of YC feedback and integration in the cultural hubs. In Aarhus, the first version of the CGJ Kit was a 'Playbook' functioning as a proof of concept tested in a 6-hour CGJ. The second version of the CGJ Kit introduced the CGJ Kit Playbook structured around the four phases of the CGJ– Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create – each supported by the transition tools – Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtesting, and Log & Pitch. CGJ Kit method cards and exercises such as cultural safaris and value-storming were developed to target the distinct game-making as culture-making activities within each phase. This version was iterated and tested across two full CGJs. The third version of the CGJ Kit will be created based on the D3.2 Protocol 2 found here, and iterations will be included based on the DBR intervention analyses and described CGJ Kit extensions (as presented in this report). This version will be tested globally across all 3 QH Cultural Hubs in Hilversum, Óbidos, and Aarhus and their three final CGJs. Results from this will lead to the fourth and final version of the CGJ Kit to be published on the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#) by the end of the project.

The Hilversum QH Cultural Hub followed the EPIC-WE four-phased approach in its 1st CGJ, drawing on the materials and methods of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit (D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#)), but also integrating other methods such as the EUija Board for exploring EU values, role cards for team specialisation, and activities like 30 Circles and LEGO tower building to foster creativity. An adapted version drawing inspiration from the CGJ Kit was created in the form of a comprehensive handbook to provide structure and encourage reflection.

Feedback from the 1st CGJ in Hilversum informed refinements for their 2nd CGJ, including adding methods such as Tarot card exercise for role assignment, streamlined brainstorming, and enhanced team planning methods. The E-P-I-C Core phases were maintained but made more flexible.

In contrast, Óbidos' 1st CGJ did not employ the CGJ Kit, but relied on the Reid et al. (2020) framework and activities like a variation of Verbs, Nouns, and Adjectives (VNA) for ideation. The 2nd CGJ integrated more structured tools, including an information kit with lagoon resources, a pre-built Unity framework to assist high school students, moodboards for thematic inspiration, and a digital adaptation of the VNA Kit. These enhancements addressed logistical and thematic integration challenges while providing participants with accessible and contextually relevant resources.

Lessons Learned from Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos Cultural Game Jams

In Aarhus, the 1st Cultural Game Jam highlighted the need for timely feedback in CGJs, as participants received input too late to make meaningful changes. Additionally, the overwhelming amount of research paperwork frustrated participants. After the 2nd jam, more precise, concise resources, such as a simplified 10-page CGJ Kit with method cards, were recommended to address these issues. Facilitators were encouraged to adopt more inclusive approaches to accommodate diverse participant needs, especially as some found digital-focused tools less accessible.

In Hilversum, the 1st Game Jam revealed the need to reduce first-day activities and improve communication about project goals. The 2nd jam encountered difficulties maintaining participant engagement, with overly long brainstorming sessions and independent assignments being poorly received. Facilitators faced challenges keeping students focused, compounded by unclear expectations and group dynamics based on friendships. While some groups connected their games to cultural heritage and themes, many struggled despite improved documentation processes. Technical misunderstandings, such as expectations for digital over paper prototypes, and delays caused by incomplete consent forms further hindered progress.

Óbidos faced unique challenges, including gender imbalance and the absence of youth stakeholders in planning during the 1st jam. Limited cultural facilitation and a broad theme made integration into games difficult. The 2nd jam highlighted technical preparedness as a significant obstacle, with high school participants struggling with inadequate equipment and unfamiliarity with Unity. Collaboration between high school and university participants also failed to materialise, signalling a need for stronger partnerships and more transparent communication across participant groups.

Future Recommendations for Cultural Game Jams from the Event Analyses

To enhance the impact and inclusivity of future CGJs, it is essential to strengthen youth participation by implementing and maintaining an empowering participatory design approach. This involves fostering closer collaboration with youth through initiatives such as the EPIC-WE Youth Advisory Boards – and the (youth) public sector in general – and engaging youth in planning CGJs such as brainstorming themes, selecting speakers, and selecting the CGJ kit approach. Furthermore, icebreaker activities or deliberate team mixing can promote better collaboration among participants from diverse backgrounds, including those from different schools, universities, disciplines or game/culture domains. A more representative gender balance should also be prioritised (i.e., corresponding to the project aims and goals of inclusion and diversity), potentially by targeted recruitment of more participants from fields such as the arts and humanities to widen the participant pool. Extended recruitment periods and targeted advertising using games, engaging visuals, and videos from previous CGJs may also attract a more diverse and representative audience.

Dedicated pre- or post-CGJ hours for completing Game Logs and other documentation requirements can be introduced to minimise disruptions. Simplified processes, such as reducing the number or length of required Game Logs or providing facilitators to assist with documentation, would streamline the experience without compromising its reflective value. Providing the organisers of CGJs with a practical handbook – besides the CGJ Kit – outlining logistical responsibilities and task distribution will further support organisational efficiency. Such requirements are met in the project by adding the practical protocol (D3.2 Protocol 4) and by stronger integration of sector perspectives and insights.

Facilitation should be enhanced to support participants more effectively through early and iterative expert feedback, cultural heritage and game design introductions, and flexible assistance that balances group and individual needs. Cultural heritage facilitation should be incorporated at every stage of CGJs –before, during, and after – through activities such as the methods found in the CGJ Kit.

Additionally, industry representatives should be encouraged to offer constructive feedback that critically challenges participants to enhance their concepts, such as facilitated by the CGJ Kit transition tools of the Expert Council and Playtesting. For those new to game-making, preparatory materials, including introductory videos and CGJ Kit methods, e.g., brainstorming, ideation, storyboarding, or prototyping, will empower them to participate confidently. Lastly, offering tailored support for analogue game creators will ensure that all participants feel equipped to succeed, regardless of their preferred game-making tools and medium. By utilising communication platforms like Discord to maintain communication and foster community engagement, CGJs can further cultivate a collaborative environment that extends beyond the event itself.

2.3 Cultural Game Jams & CGJ Kit: Sector Dimensions

From a QH Cultural Hub perspective, partners in the first half of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) included Higher Education Institutions (HEI), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI), Creative Industries (CI), and Youth Citizens (YC), both internal and external to the project, and with variations across QH Cultural Hubs and Design-Based research interventions (CGJ 1-6).

Aarhus Cultural Hub

- 1st Cultural Game Jam: The partners included ARoS (CHI), Aarhus University (HEI), Filmby Aarhus (CI), Coding Pirates (YC), Funday Games (CI), and Youth (YC). However, the youth did not take part in the planning process.
- 2nd Cultural Game Jam: The same partners participated, with Fair Games (CI) instead of Funday Games, and the addition of a Youth Advisory Board (YAB). The YAB contributed to planning, revising the CGJ Kit and facilitating the event, enabling youth to co-design alongside other QH Cultural Hub partners.

Hilversum Cultural Hub

- 1st Cultural Game Jam: The partners included Sound and Vision (CHI), DropStuff (CI), Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (HEI), and Youth (YC). CHI, CI, and HEI, but not Youth, conducted the planning.
- 2nd Cultural Game Jam: The same partners participated, but this time with the integration of a Youth Advisory Board (YAB). Two YAB members acted as expert advisors and jurors, enhancing youth empowerment and involvement in planning and organisation.

Óbidos Cultural Hub

- 1st Cultural Game Jam: Partners included Lusófona University (HEI), Battlesheep (CI), Óbidos Town Hall (CHI), and Youth (YC). Planning occurred without the involvement of Youth.
- 2nd Cultural Game Jam: The same partners participated, including high school teachers and university students representing youth. However, the youth did not engage in the planning, which was a limitation identified in the first event.

As detailed in the analyses of T2.4, youth were consistently the least involved and least integrated QH partner in the Cultural Hub collaborations, primarily limited to game-making roles during the CGJs. Introducing YABs improved youth participation, with both consultative and empowering roles and responsibilities, and involved in the process of planning, designing, being part of, and evaluating CGJs. However, to extend and refine youth involvement, QH Cultural Hubs should adopt still more demanding and authentic participatory models, involving Youth also in pre-CGJ decisions (e.g., agenda setting, theme selection, CGJ Kit composition) and CGJ practical process design, ensuring meaningful collaboration from the outset (T2.4).

The first six interventions (CGJ 1-6) highlight various strategies to integrate external partners and stakeholders into the facilitative and sector-oriented aspects of CGJs. These strategies aim to promote practical facilitation and empowering engagement with relevant industries and sectors. The CGJ Kit is a versatile game-making structure around four interrelated dimensions: values, citizenship, games, and culture. These dimensions align with the specific emphases of the different sectors. Higher education institutions focus on value-sensitive cultural methods and design and integrate intangible cultural heritage (values) into game-making. Creative industries facilitate tools, technologies, materials and support for game-making. Cultural heritage institutions are responsible for the cultural heritage sites, artefacts, stories, and materials. Youth citizens represent and enact citizenship in culture and society, bringing cultural/social themes, issues, perspectives, and identities into the CGJ.

Within the CGJ Kit, the cross-cutting W-E Dimensions of Worlds and Empowerment span all phases of the CGJ process to ensure the dual focus of cultural heritage worlds and environments and youth-empowering participation in culture and society. These overarching considerations acknowledge that each sector carries unique roles and responsibilities in applying and adapting the CGJ Kit to fit its combined local/glocal and sectoral rhythms, routines, needs, and contextual expertise, ensuring that the CGJ Kit remains flexible and responsive to diverse settings and stakeholders.

2.4 Cultural Game Jams & CGJ Kit: Local Dimensions

Facilitation Across Cultural Game Jams

Strong – both cultural and games – facilitation played a crucial role in the success of the CGJs, shaping the ideation process and enhancing participants' engagement with the themes. In each of the hubs in Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos, facilitators assisted participants through cultural exploration, guidance in game-making, and logistical support. In Aarhus, the first CGJ employed six facilitators, with cultural facilitators guiding youth in exploring cultural heritage and game-making facilitators aiding with game development aspects. However, delayed expert feedback through the Expert Council transition tool, provided nine hours into the event, constrained its effectiveness as participants hesitated to revise their games through/for culture concepts. The second Aarhus CGJ had established a youth advisory board to support the dimension of youth empowerment in the CGJ Kit and CGJ preparation and to co-lead facilitation during the CGJ, supported by researchers and creative industry partners. This approach emphasised the youth experience of a more supportive and attentive cultural heritage environment, nurturing participant empowerment and engagement through social and structured facilitation.

In Hilversum, CI and CHI stakeholders facilitated the first CGJ by organising brainstorming, paper prototyping, and expert feedback sessions. While these methods supported participants—many of whom had no prior game-making experience – some groups found the volume of feedback overwhelming. The second CGJ addressed these concerns by involving teachers as facilitators to maintain focus and enhance guidance during both the museum visit and game development phases.

Similarly, Óbidos emphasised thorough facilitation, offering cultural heritage talks, workshops, and regular check-ins during CGJs. While facilitators fostered a collaborative atmosphere through informal interactions, cultural heritage facilitators in the first CGJ were confined to the event's initial stages, limiting their impact on thematic integration. In contrast, facilitators in the second Óbidos CGJ provided ongoing support, reinforcing culture-making and game-making guidance throughout the event.

To strengthen facilitation in future CGJs, continuous support from both cultural heritage and game development facilitators should be ensured across all phases of the event (as detailed in task T2.4). Feedback sessions should be carefully timed to maximise their impact without overwhelming participants, interrupting their workflow, or immersion in the processes. As demonstrated in Aarhus, the integration of youth advisory boards should be expanded to other QH Cultural Hubs to introduce peer-led facilitation and foster inclusivity and empowerment while strengthening the youth-as-partner dimension of the QH Cultural Hubs. Facilitators should strike a balance between accessibility and non-invasiveness, empowering participants to seek help without feeling overwhelmed. Informal moments should be encouraged to create a relaxed atmosphere conducive to collaboration. Finally, cultural heritage facilitators should be included in the final EXPO showcase of the youths' games through/for culture to reflect on, evaluate, and discuss the cultural heritage integration for future development.

Cultural Game Jam Kits Across Sites

The CGJ Kit used in the CGJs at the three QH Cultural Hubs were designed to guide participants through structured phases of game creation, fostering experiential and playful processes, value-sensitivity, youth teamwork, and cultural heritage integration. In Aarhus, the first CGJ Kit is organised around the four E-P-I-C phases of the CGJ Kit: Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. Transition tools such as the Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, and Log & Pitch supported brainstorming, collaboration, feedback, and presentation. These phases were enhanced with design method cards and exercises, with examples such as cultural safari, value-storming, and rapid/rough prototyping. For the second Aarhus CGJ, the kit evolved into a comprehensive CGJ Kit made available as a digital and physical book, designed in both form and content to support the participant's different approaches and needs. It enabled participants to adapt methods and practices to their workflow. It focused on integrating EU values, game-making methods, culture-making innovation, and socio-cultural themes into their games through/for culture.

Hilversum's adaptation of the CGJ Kit adhered to the CGJ's four-phase structure, emphasising the criticality of the Expert Council and Playtesting tools. Distinctive tools included the EUija Board for exploring EU values, role cards for team specialisation and reflection (the role cards of D3.1, Protocol 2), and activities such as 30 Circles and LEGO tower building to foster creativity. A comprehensive CGJ Kit offered guidance and functioned as a reflective tool for participants. The second Hilversum CGJ improved this Kit by introducing a Tarot card exercise for role assignment, streamlining brainstorming activities, and enhancing team planning through sticky notes and guidelines while preserving the core phases and transitions of EPIC-WE CGJs.

The Óbidos hub applied a distinct approach in its first CGJ, utilising a variation of the Verbs, Nouns, and Adjectives (VNA) tool during the pre-jam, while following the [Reid et al. \(2020\)](#) framework for applied game jams to guide the overall process. By the second Óbidos CGJ, additional tools were incorporated, including an information package with QR codes for contextual background, a pre-built Unity framework to expedite game creation for secondary school students, moodboards for visual inspiration, and a digital variation of the VNA Kit to enhance brainstorming. During these CGJs, the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit was not utilised.

It is advised (T2.4) that all QH Cultural Hubs share the methods used, which are currently external to the CGJ Kit, and consider integrating these into the kit. This exchange of ideas and collaboration would facilitate the adoption of best CGJ practices and ensure consistent support across CGJs while allowing for customisation to local contexts and participant needs.

2.5 Cultural Game Jams & CGJ Kit: Glocal Dimensions

A vital component of the evolution of EPIC-WE, particularly regarding developing a Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (see D3.2, Protocol 1 and D3.1 [Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation](#)), has been the establishment of local youth advisory boards (YABs). YABs enable interaction and foster a glocal entity to support, participate in, and critique the collaborative and designerly approaches and the CGJs as design interventions. From T2.4, a key lesson is that to effectively engage and empower youth already in the preparation phase of the game jam, it is crucial to clearly define their roles, responsibilities, and decision power and establish clear communication and structured processes for their empowered participation. The EPIC-WE YAB approach promotes the inclusion and empowerment of youth while safeguarding the research objectives and ensuring the integration of cultural themes.

To enable and support the impact and inclusivity of glocal CGJs, several strategies identified in the analyses of T4.3 and T2.4 should be integrated into the CGJ Kit. As mentioned, further strengthening youth's empowered participation is a critical step. Therefore, establishing a glocal Youth Advisory Board (YAB) through local YABs and involving youth participants in the planning activities – such as brainstorming themes, selecting speakers and workshops, and designing the CGJ experience and set-up – can foster an empowering participatory approach in CGJs.

Proper and practical preparation before the CGJ is vital for smoother execution. Providing complementary introductory materials, such as videos on game design basics, the EPIC-WE approach, the CGJ Kit, the CGJ theme, and cultural heritage sites and collections, would help participants—particularly those without prior game jam experience—feel more confident.

Facilitation during the CGJ is marked as another area for improvement. Inviting experts in culture, arts, gaming, and game design to provide early critical feedback to enable youth to revise and refine their games afterward through/for culture concepts before beginning to prototype the final game can enhance the quality of the final outputs. Strengthening cultural heritage facilitation throughout the event - through pitch sessions, tours in the exhibitions, individual group feedback, and ongoing support – fosters deeper engagement with, integration of, and expressivity in the cultural heritage themes. Encouraging industry representatives to deliver constructive and detailed game design critiques can also challenge participants to critically evaluate their games through/for culture and thus identify needed external expertise to secure productive and culturally rich CGJ experiences.

Efforts to foster inclusivity and diversity should be expanded (see also part of the D3.2, Protocol 4). From a CGJ process perspective, early joint activities and team-mixing strategies can promote collaboration across different cultural and educational backgrounds. Tailored and flexible support for participants with varying skill levels and creative approaches is essential. Novice game designers would benefit from the CGJ kits' accessible ideation exercises and workshops, while those developing analogue games should receive specialised CGJ Kit methods and guidance that reflect the diversity of game-making traditions.

The identified CGJ principles (see ‘Fundamental Principles for Cultural Game Jams’ in this report) should be adhered to and guide the organisation and running of CGJs to ensure compliance with the EPIC-WE aims and objectives and the creation of games through/for culture. Empowering youth through active participation - such as establishing a glocal Youth Advisory Board and involving young people in the planning and running of CGJs – ensures meaningful integration of a ‘global’ CGJ Kit in ‘local’ cultural heritage sites and connecting these through ‘glocal’ strategies.

Continuous focus on cultural integration is significant, with experts and facilitators offering early and ongoing support during the initial CGJ phases, constructive feedback during the whole process, and activities that deeply embed cultural themes into the game jam and design process. These approaches towards further refining the CGJ Kit collectively foster collaboration among the QH Cultural Hub partners and stakeholders, connecting global-local elements to create impactful and empowering glocal CGJs.

Through the EPIC-WE project Milestone 4 in 2024 of conceptualising the glocal approach of EPIC-WE, multiple approaches to manifesting glocality in future CGJs were developed. These were reviewed, and the EPIC-WE project’s Executive Board selected four glocal initiatives as a way forward towards increased glocality of the second round of CGJs:

1. enabling a shared digital communication environment across hubs,
2. collectively exploring and deciding on joint cultural heritage or citizen themes,
3. securing and empowering local youth advisory board members to participate in a glocal YAB, and
4. following and integrating the same and shared protocols (D3.2, Protocol 1-4) and the CGJ Kit.

2.6 Overview of CGJ Kit Elements

As mentioned in the beginning of this report, the initial D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) developed, described, and delivered:

A EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Phases

Experience Phase

- Focuses on cultural exploration, encouraging participants to engage with cultural heritage sites, artifacts, narratives, and values.
- Uses developed game-making and culture-making methods such as valuestorming, love letters, and culture safarito inspire game concepts through/for culture.

Play Phase

- Centres on playful experimentation with gameplay ideas, mechanics, aesthetics, and narratives.
- Uses developed methods such as culture collage, 6-8-5 game sketching, and storyboarding.

Imagine Phase

- Involves refining and materialising game ideas into tangible prototypes.
- Uses developed methods such as citizen experience mapping, cultural provotyping, and game mock-ups.

Create Phase

- Participants produce a playable game for game players to experience culture through games and games for culture.
- Focuses on documentation, final adjustments, and showcasing the games at the concluding CGJ EXPO

B EPIC-WE Dimensions: World and Empowerment

- **World Dimension:** Focuses on experience of and interaction with cultural gameworlds, storytelling, and values.
- **Empowerment Dimension:** Encourages youth to engage culture and cultural heritage with empowered participation, enabling them to become co-creators of games and culture, fostering creativity, agency, and critical engagement.

C EPIC-WE Transition Tools

- **Ideation Wheel:** Helps participants transition from the Experience phase and experience and generate multiple ideas through exploring culture, values, citizenship, and game topics.
- **Expert Council:** Helps participants transition from the Play phase and provides them with feedback from experts and professionals in games and culture targeting the intersection of these.
- **Playtest:** Helps participants transition from the Imagine phase and enables the iterative refinement of the game concept by constructing mock-ups or prototypes that allow participants to test and adjust their games through/for culture based on playtesting.
- **Log & Pitch:** Helps participants transition from the Create phase and prepare them for the online publication of their game on the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#) and the concluding EXPO showcasing their games through/for culture.

D EPIC-WE Core Categories: Culture, Games, Values, and Citizenship

The CGJ Kit and its methods are structured around four core categories, aligning with the **Quadruple Helix Model**, which integrates perspectives and elements from:

- **Creative Industries (CIs):** Experts in game design, gameplay, and digital media.
- **Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs):** Experts in cultural heritage, narratives, and contexts.
- **Higher Education Institutions (HEIs):** Experts in value-sensitive design, research methodologies, and educational activities.
- **Youth Citizens (YCs):** Bring their lived experiences, creativity, and perspectives to co-create games through/for culture.

The final D3.2 Protocol 2 extends the CGJ Kit from the initial D3.1 Protocol 2 by:

1. Adding **local, glocal, and sector dimensions** to the CGJ Kit, as described above, to enhance local-glocal use and contextual sensitivity.
2. Defining the **fundamental principles** for Cultural Game Jams to ensure understanding of what distinguishes and characterises the format.
3. Organising the CGJ Kit into a **focused, flexible, and freeform format** to enable adaptability to concrete and different events and activities formats.
4. Dividing the CGJ Kit into a **Games through Culture Kit** and a **Games for Culture Kit** will target the two main domains of the CGJ Kit: Cultural heritage and engagement.

2.7 Fundamental Principles for Cultural Game Jams

Seven fundamental principles can be synthesised from the first half of the EPIC-WE project's research and innovation efforts, its first six Design-Based Research interventions (CGJ 1-6), and its conceptualisation of QH cultural hubs, cultural game jams, and games through and for culture. These fundamental CGJ principles should guide the organisation and running of CGJs and the use of the CGJ Kit to ensure compliance with the EPIC-WE aims and objectives and the creation of games through/for culture.

1 Principle 1: Three ways to run Cultural Game Jams

Cultural Game Jams embrace a structured yet adjustable approach to game-making as culture-making, offering three levels of adaptability:

- **Fixed**, where Cultural Game Jam elements are determined at the project or organisational level
- **Flexible**, where the QH Cultural Hub tailor the process to local needs
- **Freeform**, where youth shape their creative and collaborative journey based on the Cultural Game Jam Kit.

These levels operate within a minimum viable model, balancing guidance and exploration. The Cultural Game Jam phases - Experience, Play, Imagine, Create - provide a straightforward yet open-ended process, allowing participants to engage with cultural themes and heritage by creating games through and for culture. Transition tools like the Ideation Wheel and Expert Council help participants transition from one phase to the next while refining ideas and integrating feedback and decisions.

2 Principle 2: Aim for cultural participation, co-creation, and empowerment

Cultural Game Jams position game-making as an act of cultural imagination and creation, where youth are not just receivers or consumers of heritage but active creators and contributors to shaping its future. Participants engage in a co-creative process that positions game-making as a new form of culture-making through which youth create and showcase games through and for culture. These games directly engage cultural heritage, using it as an empowering medium for game-making. This participatory approach fosters a sense of ownership and belonging, allowing youth to engage, reinterpret, and comment on cultural heritage through game-making in ways that reflect their own experiences and identities. By designing games that reflect their lived experiences, values, and collective imaginaries, participants develop a stronger sense of agency and belonging in cultural heritage and within cultural environments.

3

Principle 3: Foster cultural curiosity and creativity

Cultural Game Jams cultivate an environment where curiosity and creativity drive cultural exploration, encouraging youth to become culture-makers through cultural storytelling and game design. The game-making process fosters deep engagement with past, present, and future cultural narratives by allowing participants to experiment, remix, and reimagine cultural heritage by creating games through and for culture. Through Cultural Game Jams, culture is not a static artefact of the past but an evolving and participatory practice that youth actively shape by creating cultural experiences, interactions, and expressions.

4

Principle 4: Cultivate an “epic we” through Cultural Game Jams

Cultural Game Jams are designed to cultivate a sense of community and collective creativity that transcends the individual to foster an experience of becoming part of an "epic we" in cultural heritage. This approach requires creating conditions encouraging collaboration, relational engagement and shared cultural exploration, where differences interact generatively rather than competitively. By embracing tensions and dissimilarities as opportunities for cultural curiosity and co-creation, Cultural Game Jams become more than game-making events – they serve as transformative cultural environments that nurture engaged participation, cultural empowerment, and collective culture-making.

5

Principle 5: Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making

At the heart of Cultural Game Jams is a commitment to value-sensitive cultural design, where cultural, ethical, and societal considerations shape the game-making process. Participants are encouraged to critically engage and examine themes such as citizenship, European identity, and cultural heritage's evolving and participatory nature. And to engage this through a co-creative approach and the creation of games through and for culture. Participants explore how cultural heritage and values are embedded in and expressed through game mechanics, interactions, narratives, and aesthetics. This, in turn, fosters a deeper awareness of how games, through and for culture, can function as a method for cultural critique, reflectivity, expression, and empowerment.

6

Principle 6: Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation

Cultural Game Jams challenge more audience-oriented notions of cultural heritage by engaging game-making as a powerful method for action-oriented cultural engagement. Rather than approaching heritage as something to be preserved, admired, or consumed, Cultural Game Jams invite participants to reimagine, remix, remediate, and recreate cultural works and narratives in their games through and for culture. This approach highlights the potential of games as interactive systems and experiences. As such, they can provoke thought, spark dialogue, and interactively engage audiences as players with and within cultural heritage. By embedding cultural inquiry, interpretation, and innovation into the game-making process, Cultural Game Jams contribute to a broader recognition of games' potential as culture and within cultural heritage.

7

Principle 7: Create games through and for culture and cultural transformation

Cultural Game Jams position game-making as a reflection of and active engagement with culture, resulting in the creation of games through and for culture. By embedding historical, imaginative, and societal themes in games and inviting game-makers to engage with heritage through cultural transformation, Cultural Game Jams results in games through and for culture that serve as immersive cultural storytelling forms. This dual focus on games through culture (exploring and incorporating cultural heritage as game-making material towards new interactive cultural expressions) and games for culture (imagining and enacting values, identities, and collective responsibility in culture and society) ensures that Cultural Game Jams and their resulting games are not only about transmission of cultural heritage but are also integral to its ongoing transformation and evolution.

The Focused,
Flexible,
and Freeform
CGJ Kit

03

3. The Focused, Flexible, and Freeform CGJ Kit

3.1 Results and Insights from CGJ 1-6: The CGJ Kit

The necessity of providing opportunities for structured and adaptable versions of CGJs has emerged from the results of the first round of Design-Based interventions (CGJ 1-6), carried out within the three QH Cultural Hubs. This result – and the need for focused, flexible, as well as freeform compositions of the CGJ Kit – emerges from the local analyses of cultural themes within a QH Cultural Hub (thematic analyses of all collected data), the local analyses of individual cultural events (case analyses of CGJ 1-6), and analyses of each of the created games through/for culture (T4.3). This is further substantiated by the glocal cross-hub analysis, which looks at all thematic analyses, cultural events, and games to identify shared and unique results and insights (T2.4). This is further informed by feedback and recommendations from the six focus group workshops with CHI, CI, and HEI (T3.4), where all QH Cultural Hub partners shared insights and reflections.

Depending on the length, type, complexity, resources, facilitators, background of participants, etc., of a specific CGJ, a focused, flexible, or freeform composition of the CGJ Kit might be desirable. Some might find a simple one-track composition where everything is settled in advance, static and disempowering or clear and empowering. Likewise, some might find an open and free choice composition where the composition of the CGJ Kit is up to the participants to be chaotic and disempowering or liberating and empowering.

A rigid CGJ process with predefined methods and tools can disrupt the creative flow, mainly when time constraints or fluctuations in group energy and engagement occur. Allowing for flexibility ensures that the CGJ remains engaging, fostering creativity and maintaining momentum.

Feedback from participants and facilitators highlighted that when methods are excessively structured, they can hinder participants' immersion in the game-making process. Still, a **focused CGJ Kit** can also provide structure, security, and clarity for those less experienced. For others, a **flexible CGJ Kit** approach can be seen as more empowering by permitting some improvisation and allowing non-essential methods to be bypassed or adapted without compromising the overall objectives of the CGJ. This flexibility fosters a more organic flow, enabling participants to engage with the event in ways that feel most productive, thus supporting empowered participation.

However, it also risks losing the strong focus and straightforward instructional design of the focused CGJ Kit. In the flexible CGJ Kit, facilitators must be prepared to assess the dynamics of the group and make real-time decisions about when to adapt methods or omit certain activities. Finally, facilitators might also want to leave the decision power with the youth participants by giving them control over the full **freeform CGJ Kit**. Here, teams can pick and choose the methods in each phase. As such, the final CGJ Kit will contain a focused, flexible, and freeform composition mode to ensure broad applicability, versatile adaptability, and context- and participant-sensitive CGJ Kit options.

In the T2.4 analysis of CGJ 1-6 several opportunities for refinement of the CGJ Kit are identified. To optimise facilitation in CGJs, it is vital to ensure continuous support from facilitators throughout the entire event, not just during specific phases like ideation or feedback.

CGJ design and facilitation should strike a balance between participant autonomy and directedness. Tailored approaches are necessary to meet the diverse needs of participants, as observed throughout the CGJ 1-6 interventions. Facilitators should avoid mandatory or overly intrusive involvement, instead fostering a culture where participants feel empowered to seek help when needed. Informal interactions and relaxed moments should be encouraged to create a comfortable atmosphere for cultural heritage exploration and game experimentation. Cultural facilitators should also participate in the final EXPO, which showcases the created games through/for culture.

Moving between focused, flexible, and freeform approaches to the CGJ Kit enables CGJ organisers and facilitators to strategically enhance participants' ability to engage meaningfully with the cultural heritage themes and values. Ultimately, empowering participants to take ownership of the CGJ process and their game-making as culture-making – by being supported (focused), guided (flexible), or uninhibited (freeform) – ensures that the CGJs remains responsive and attuned to participants needs, skills and background as well as the configuration of the cultural heritage site, collections, fostering a more empowering and inclusive atmosphere.

Cultural Game Jams embrace a structured yet adjustable approach to game-making as culture-making, offering three levels of adaptability:

Focused

- where all CGJ elements are determined at the project or organisational level – this also contains the minimum viable model for the CGJ Kit);

Flexible

- where the QH Cultural Hub tailor the process to local needs; and

Freeform

- where youth shape their own creative and collaborative journey based on the CGJ Kit.

These levels operate within a minimum viable model, balancing guidance and exploration. The Cultural Game Jam phases - Experience, Play, Imagine, Create - provide a straightforward yet open-ended process, allowing participants to engage with cultural themes and cultural heritage by creating games through and for culture. Transition tools like the Ideation Wheel and Expert Council help participants transition from one phase to the next while refining ideas and integrating feedback and decisions. By combining structured support with space for experimentation, Cultural Game Jams is designed to empower youth to confidently navigate the complexities of cultural game design while fostering a dynamic and exploratory creative process.

The following sections describe the focused, flexible, and freeform CGJ Kit compositions. They will then be implemented as an extension in the next version of the CGJ Kit.

3.2 The Focused CGJ Kit

The focused CGJ Kit operates at the EPIC-WE project level, and contains the mandatory CGJ model with phases, methods, transition tools, value cards, and game logs. The focused CGJ Kit is the backbone of any CGJ and constitutes the minimum viable composition for running a CGJ.

A fixed and focused toolkit for CGJs is a highly structured framework in which all participants adhere to the same mandatory CGJ. This approach is designed to maintain consistency, ensure alignment with EPIC-WE's aims and objectives, and provide clear developmental steps for creating games through/for culture throughout the game-making process.

Advantages of Focused Cultural Game Jams

Consistency and Quality: By following a set of mandatory methods and processes, a focus on the EPIC-WE core concepts and consistent quality across all games through/for culture can be ensured. This is particularly important for cultural game jams, where game-making as culture-making and respect for cultural heritage, themes, and values are paramount.

Efficiency: A fixed CGJ Kit streamlines the development process, reducing the time spent on CGJ organisation before the event, and participants' decision-making during the event. This provides security for participants unfamiliar with game jams, game design, or games through/for culture, and allows participants to focus on cultural creativity and transformation rather than decision-making.

Competence Development: Participants can learn and apply a thoroughly iterated and well-tested CGJ Kit, developed through the 12 Design-Based Research interventions (CGJ 1-12), enhancing their culture-making and game-making skills and competences.

Collaboration: Structured CGJ team roles, methods, and processes facilitate better collaboration and co-creation among team members. Every member can take on dedicated roles, is supported in their work by the GJ Kit, and understands the workflow through the four E-P-I-C phases.[RN1]

One of the primary advantages of a fixed toolkit is **consistency and quality**. By following a standardised sequence of activities, every team produces outcomes that meet uniform standards, which is essential for upholding the EPIC-WE goals of the project. Another benefit is the **scaffolded guidance for beginners**. New participants, or those less familiar with game jams or game design, benefit from having straightforward, predefined methods and processes. This reduces uncertainty, allowing them to focus on cultural-creative expression within a focused framework. In addition, a focused CGJ Kit promotes **efficient time management**. With set phases and tasks, the CGJ progresses smoothly, minimising delays and preventing confusion. Furthermore, the systematic nature of the focused CGJ Kit facilitates the **attainment of competencies and skills along with focused culture and game development**. This standardisation also aids in uniform documentation and publication of games through/for culture and enables sharing best practices across different sites.

Disadvantages of Focused Cultural Game Jams

Creativity Constraints: Mandatory methods and processes can sometimes stifle creativity, as participants may feel restricted by the fixed process and unable to explore ideas or processes not supported by the CGJ Kit.

Inflexibility: A fixed CGJ Kit may not accommodate the unique needs and preferences of all cultural heritage sites or CGJ participants, leading to frustration and reduced engagement.

Overhead: The time and effort required to learn and adhere to the CGJ Kit and processes can be a burden, particularly for novice organisers, facilitators, and participants.

Despite its strengths, a focused CGJ Kit can also be limiting. The rigid structure may lead to **limited creativity**, as participants might feel constrained by the mandatory steps and unable to deviate or change things spontaneously. This is particularly challenging for experienced individuals who may have unique insights that fall outside the prescribed methods. Additionally, the CGJ Kit's standardised nature can result in a **lack of contextual adaptation**. A one-size-fits-all approach might not accommodate the diverse cultural settings, participant needs, or specific themes present in different European contexts. Such inflexibility can hinder the authentic representation of local cultural heritage nuances. There is also the risk of **participant disengagement**. Some participants may perceive the mandatory processes as overly rigid, which can diminish empowerment and hinder deeper cultural-creative exploration.

Structure Based on the CGJ Kit

The focused toolkit is structured around the CGJ Kit's defined E-P-I-C phases:

- **Experience Phase:** Participants engage in mandatory cultural exploration activities. The included methods and transition tool are designed to experience a deep understanding of local culture and values.
- **Play Phase:** Participants use methods to translate cultural-creative insights and first ideas into initial game concepts. The included methods and transition tool are designed to play with ideas and get critical feedback on initial game concepts.
- **Imagine Phase:** Participants use methods to create a mock-up or prototype that can undergo playtesting. This structured approach ensures that each team produces a comparable level of detail in their games through/for culture, facilitating game-making as culture-making.
- **Create Phase:** A detailed presentation format and standardised documentation game logs are provided. Predefined templates guide teams towards releasing their final game through/for culture at the onsite EXPO and the online EPIC-WE Resource Site, ensuring that all outputs meet uniform quality standards and are aligned with the overall culture-making and game-making objectives of CGJs.[]

Developing the focused CGJ Kit involved revising the initial CGJ Kit from D3.1 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit to identify and construct the focused CGJ Kit.

3.3 The Flexible CGJ Kit

The flexible CGJ Kit operates at the **EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hub level**. It allows each hub to expand the mandatory focused CGJ Kit with methods and role cards to highlight specific methods, themes, or categories.

A flexible CGJ Kit offers the possibility for QH Cultural Hubs to curate a set of add-on methods to the focused CGJ Kit that help the QH Cultural Hub organisers and facilitators adapt the CGJ Kit to their specific needs, context, location, and participant background. This approach strikes a balance between structure and adaptability, ensuring that the core framework is aligned with the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit and maintained while allowing for local customisation.

Advantages of a Flexible CGJ Kit

Adaptability: A flexible CGJ Kit can be customised to fit the specific cultural heritage context, the CGJ location, and the participants' backgrounds, ensuring the process is relevant and engaging.

Creativity: By offering a variety of methods and processes that the QH Cultural Hub can choose from, a flexible CGJ Kit enables organisers, facilitators, and participants to explore unconventional ideas and approaches, fostering cultural transformation and innovation.

Inclusivity: A flexible CGJ Kit can accommodate participants with diverse skill levels, backgrounds, identities, disciplines, and preferences, making the CGJ more inclusive and accessible.

Inclusivity: A flexible CGJ Kit can accommodate participants with diverse skill levels, backgrounds, identities, disciplines, and preferences, making the CGJ more inclusive and accessible.

Resource Optimization: Organisers can select the most appropriate set-up of the flexible CGJ Kit based on the available resources, ensuring efficient use of time and materials.

The primary advantage of a flexible toolkit is its **contextual relevance**. Organisers can choose from the catalogue of pretested CGJ methods to suit best the local cultural environment, themes, and participant needs and preferences. This adaptable approach enables the QH Cultural Hub organisers and facilitators to integrate culturally specific methods and processes, ensuring the game-making process resonates with local heritage and societal values. It also encourages innovation, as methods can be mixed and matched to stimulate cultural creativity while providing enough structure to guide the process. Additionally, the toolkit's adaptability allows for real-time adjustments during the game jam - if a particular method isn't yielding the desired results, an alternative can be quickly implemented. Another key benefit is its ability to accommodate both beginners and experienced participants. While a core structure remains intact, the availability of multiple options means that organisers can select less intimidating methods for newcomers or more challenging for seasoned game-makers depending on the particular constellation of participants' backgrounds, disciplines and skillsets.

Disadvantages of a Flexible CGJ Kit

Complexity: The wide range of options in a flexible toolkit can be overwhelming for both organisers and facilitators.

Inconsistency: Without a standardised process, the quality and consistency of the games produced may vary, which can be a concern for organisers aiming for a certain level of quality. Therefore, the flexible CGJ Kit is built on top of the focused CGJ Kit.

Learning Curve: Participants may need to spend additional time learning and adapting to the additional methods, which can be a challenge, especially for novice game-makers.

However, the flexible approach can lead to **inconsistencies** between different CGJs. The freedom to choose methods from a broad palette means that outcomes may vary, making it harder to compare results or maintain a unified standard across CGJs. The success of this approach heavily relies on the expertise of the organisers and facilitators. Selecting the most appropriate methods for a given context requires significant knowledge and experience; less experienced organisers and facilitators might inadvertently choose methods that do not integrate well, leading to a fragmented or unfocused process.

Moreover, a flexible CGJ Kit demands **longer preparation times**. Organisers must evaluate the various methods, assess their suitability, and sometimes conduct trial runs before finalising the kit's composition. This planning phase can be resource-intensive and may necessitate additional training or consultation with experts from cultural heritage and creative industries.

Overall, the flexible toolkit offers a balanced approach that maintains a solid structural foundation while enabling adaptation to diverse cultural contexts. This balance encourages both consistency in process and creativity in outcomes, making it a valuable option for tailoring CGJs to specific local needs.

The development of the flexible CGJ Kit involved revising the initial CGJ Kit from D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) to identify and construct the flexible CGJ Kit.

3.4 The Freeform Kit

The freeform CGJ Kit operates at the **EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam level** and allows each team to freely choose from all available methods while maintaining the mandatory focused CGJ Kit.

A free CGJ Kit provides agency and autonomy to participants, empowering them to explore and choose methods that best suit their cultural heritage interests, game concepts, and team dynamics. Here, the CGJ Kit serves more as a repository of diverse methods and techniques collected in the full CGJ Kit from which teams can freely select what they find most interesting, relevant, and meaningful.

Advantages of a Freeform CGJ Kit

Personalisation: Youth participants can tailor the CGJ process to their specific needs, interests, and intentions, resulting in a more engaging and inspiring experience.

Creativity: By allowing participants to choose their own methods and processes, a participant-driven CGJ Kit encourages exploration and experimentation, fostering culturally unique and creative game concepts.

Empowerment: Participants are more likely to be empowered and feel belonging in cultural heritage CGJs when they have the freedom to select methods and compose their own game-making as culture-making journey.

Skill Development: Participants can focus on developing competencies and skills that are most relevant to their personal and professional goals, enhancing their overall learning experience.

The most significant advantage of a freeform toolkit is the **maximum creative freedom** it offers. Participants can define their own game-making as culture-making journey, fostering deep engagement and personal ownership of the creative process. This participant-centred approach encourages teams to tailor the process to reflect their unique cultural heritage narratives, aesthetics, gameplay and systems, resulting in outputs highly reflective of their individual and collective cultural belonging.

Additionally, the freeform CGJ Kit's adaptability allows teams to choose methods that align with their local cultural contexts, values, and identities, ensuring the game-making process is contextually relevant and dynamic. This inherent flexibility also promotes exploration and experimentation – key drivers of innovation and transformation in creative practices – by enabling teams to modify or abandon methods that do not work for them in real time.

Disadvantages of a Flexible CGJ Kit

Inconsistency: The lack of pre-selected and organised methods and processes can lead to variability in the quality and consistency of the games produced through/for culture, which may concern organisers.

Complexity: The wide range of options can overwhelm participants, potentially leading to decision fatigue and confusion.

Resource Management: Organisers and facilitators may find it challenging to ensure that all participants have access to all necessary resources, materials, and expert support for their chosen methods.

Despite these benefits, the freeform CGJ Kit carries certain risks. **The lack of structure** can lead to disorganisation or decision fatigue, or paralysis especially among less experienced teams that may struggle to establish a coherent process, potentially resulting in uneven outcomes. Without clear guidelines, some participants may produce fragmented outputs. Moreover, the variability in method selection can lead to inconsistent quality, making it challenging for organisers to provide uniform support or help realise the games through/for culture across diverse groups – each with their own CGJ process. For beginners, the absence of structured guidance might be overwhelming, which could impede progress and compromise the overall effectiveness of the game jam.

However, even within the freeform CGJ Kit, the foundational framework of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit remains as a guiding structure, though it is not strictly enforced. The freeform CGJ Kit best suits highly engaged, experienced participants who thrive on creative autonomy and self-directed innovation. To mitigate potential disorganisation, facilitators might offer optional support or checkpoints, providing minimal scaffolding while preserving the complete freedom that characterises the free toolkit approach.

This toolkit provides a highly adaptable framework that can help participants create innovative, culturally rich games while fostering a personalised, engaging game development experience.

The development of the freeform CGJ Kit involved revising the initial CGJ Kit from D3.1 [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#) to identify and construct the freeform CGJ Kit.

Key Differences between the Focused, Flexible, and Freeform CGJ Kit

- **Control:** The focused CGJ kit is controlled by the project, while the organisers or facilitators control the flexible CGJ Kit within a QH Cultural Hub, who then tailor the CGJ process to the context and participants, while the freeform toolkit gives control to the youth participants to choose methods that suit their needs and interests.
- **Adaptability vs. Personalisation:** The focused CGJ Kit is not adaptable as it is the minimum viable process and mandatory backbone of a CGJ. The flexible CGJ Kit adapts to the overall context, constellation and culture of the QH Cultural Hub. In contrast, the freeform CGJ Kit is highly personalised to cater to individual participants' preferences.
- **Empowerment and Engagement:** The freeform CGJ Kit may increase empowerment and engagement, as participants have more freedom and agency to choose methods that interest them.
- **Consistency and Quality:** The flexible toolkit may offer more consistency and quality control, while the participant-driven toolkit may lead to more outcome variability.

By understanding these differences, organisers and facilitators can choose or compose the most appropriate CGJ Kit for their Cultural Game Jam, ensuring a balance between structure and freedom that best suits their goals and participants.

GAME-MAKING AS CULTURE MAKING

04

4. Game-making as Culture-making

4.1 Game-making as culture-making?

D3.1, [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#), defines and highlights “game-making as a form of culture-making that develops cultural engagement, creativity, and empowered participation through CGJ processes, methods, and tools” (p. 10), leading to the dual outcome of games for and through culture as equal forms of new cultural expressions to preserve, extend, innovate, and transform cultural heritage.

Game-making within the EPIC-WE project is framed as an innovative and empowering form of culture-making, where young citizens, cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and higher education institutions collaborate closely to enable youth to create games through/for culture using cultural heritage, issues, themes, and values as game-making material. This process is embedded within the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam framework, which positions game-making as an active, iterative, and co-creative engagement with culture, values, and identity.

At its core, game-making as culture-making involves the intentional design of games through/for culture that both emerge from and contribute to cultural heritage. Games serve as a dynamic medium for cultural experiences, interactions and storytelling, allowing participants to **reinterpret cultural heritage narratives, challenge dominant cultural perspectives, and explore new modes of engagement with culture and heritage.**

The EPIC-WE project leverages this by fostering **value-and culture-sensitive game-making methodologies**, ensuring that the CGJs and the creation of games through/for culture are empowering through facilitating cultural value, meaning, dialogue, and transformation. Through the **World and Empowerment Dimensions** of the CGJ Kit, games through/for culture are framed as reflective of broader cultural and societal issues, themes, and identities. The **World Dimension** emphasises the role of games in shaping and representing cultural worlds and environments, while the **Empowerment Dimension** highlights their potential to foster agency, inclusivity, identity, and belonging. The dual focus on games through culture (using cultural heritage as game-making material) and games for culture (engaging, participating and transforming culture and society) ensures that the games created are not just entertainment products but meaningful cultural interventions.

The EPIC-WE project is grounded in understanding games as cultural worlds with the ability to influence our sense of being, ethics, values, and identities, both within and beyond the game environment. They have the capacity to enculturate players, foster cultural appreciation, and act as agents of change. Games can be transformative by promoting diversity and offering spaces for community, empathy, and belonging.

To engage young people with the EU's cultural heritage and values, cultural institutions can leverage games and game-making as a means of cultural empowerment and participation, a concept we term 'cultural game jams' (CGJs). Such cultural game jams enable young participants to become culture-makers through game-making practices in the CGJ by integrating tangible and intangible heritage into their games through/for culture. By collaborating with youth within Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems, CHI and CI can encourage youth to explore and embrace game-making as a form of artistic cultural heritage expression. This collaborative approach can contribute to shaping new game cultures, nurturing diverse cultural voices and identities, and reflecting and facilitating societal and cultural transformations.

The twin concepts of 'games through culture' and 'games for culture' emphasise the role games and game-making can have in cultural engagement and empowerment. **Games through culture** focuses on employing cultural heritage as game-making material. Via the creation of games through culture, youth engage directly with integrating and transforming cultural heritage into cultural heritage gameplay experiences and interactions, game narratives, aesthetics, systems, and gameworlds. In this way, such game-making practices can transmit, transform, or transcend the aesthetics, narratives, histories, composition, and qualities of cultural heritage, positioning youth as engaged culture-makers who shape new cultural heritage expressions through games. Similarly, **games for culture** focuses on creating games that address, express, or reinterpret cultural or societal themes or issues. Via culture- and value-sensitive practices, youth are positioned as citizens directly involved in the (re)configuration of culture and society through game-making practices. Through developing gameplay experiences and interactions, game narratives, aesthetics, systems, and gameworlds, youth are empowered to express their cultural voices, identities, belonging, and citizenship through creating a game for culture. Overall, the main focus of youth as game-makers and culture-makers is

- to experience and engage in tangible and intangible **cultural heritage** as game-making material for the creation of games through culture
- to experience and engage **cultural- and value-sensitive citizenship** through game-making as a form of culture-making, positioning themselves as empowered citizens in cultural worlds through creating games for culture.

By positioning game-making as a form of culture-making, the CGJs demonstrate that games can be **living cultural expressions** that shape, reflect, and transform how we understand and engage with heritage, values, and identity. The CGJ Kit transforms traditional game jams into **cultural engagement and innovation**.

4.2 Results and Insights from CGJ 1-6: From 1 to 2 CGJ Kits

This section presents key findings and insights from the CGJs across three distinct cultural hubs: Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum. It highlights the interplay between cultural integration, facilitation, and participant engagement, providing a comparative analysis of how these elements influenced the success of the CGJs, connecting them to local, glocal, and sectoral dimensions. While Aarhus demonstrated the transformative potential of games as cultural artefacts and platforms for creative storytelling, Óbidos underscored the critical role of consistent facilitation in sustaining cultural integration. In Hilversum, challenges in embedding cultural insights into gameplay mechanics revealed tensions between preserving and innovating cultural heritage. Common themes across all hubs emphasise the necessity for value-sensitive facilitation, accessible resources, and participant empowerment to ensure meaningful engagement with cultural content.

Aarhus: The integration of cultural and artistic elements was prominent, with participants exploring how games could reflect cultural heritage, values, and creative narratives, as well as how they might experientially and effectively respond to cultural heritage. The setting of the art museum inspired experimental storytelling and highlighted the potential of games as cultural artefacts, resonating with participants, even those without backgrounds in cultural, art, or humanities disciplines, thereby demonstrating signs of empowered participation in culture. The interplay between culture, games, and values enabled participants to investigate societal themes and utilise game design as a medium for cultural storytelling and value expression. Social and collaborative engagement was a cornerstone of the CGJ's experiences, as highlighted in the T4.3 and T2.4 analyses, fostering teamwork, networking, socialisation, and collective creativity. Diverse group dynamics encouraged participants to transition from simple cultural ideas to complex, multi-layered narratives, particularly when prompted by reflective themes such as "What does it mean to be human – and how might that be expressed through games?" which were significantly related to the cultural exhibition of "Human Nature". The balance between autonomy and collaboration, especially in the second iteration of the CGJ at Aarhus, nurtured participant engagement and allowed for the meaningful application of expertise from other creative fields.

Óbidos: Facilitation emerged as a vital factor in the success of the cultural game jam. Facilitators were crucial during the early phases, guiding participants through cultural visits and ideation. However, their diminished involvement in the later stages restricted participants' capacity to maintain deep cultural integration in their games, highlighting the necessity for ongoing facilitation throughout the event. Youth participants, through surveys and interviews, stated that facilitators were a key element during the entire Cultural Game Jam. In Óbidos, two types of facilitators contributed to the process: cultural facilitators and game-making facilitators. Cultural facilitators were chosen according to the theme of the game jam. They were the main actors during the pre-game jam activities, which included cultural visits through Óbidos, lectures on the theme and preparing informational materials. Besides cultural facilitators, game-making facilitators were also present throughout the event, providing any kind of help necessary, ranging from technical assistance with itch.io, logistical problems with residences, food or space, but also in the process of ideation and using game engines.

The facilitators' positive impact on the participants' overall experience reveals that their presence should be continuously reinforced in the next game jams. For example, cultural facilitators should be present at other key moments, such as pitch sessions or extending the number of hours at the facility.

Hilversum: Participants engaged with societal and cultural themes, touching on inequality and environmental concerns. However, many struggled to embed these insights deeply into gameplay mechanics, whereas issues resided in the direct cultural integration of the games. This, however, highlights a tension between the preservation and innovation of cultural heritage, where one might be easier to identify in a game prototype (those close to the cultural artefact or site) and one perhaps transmitting or mediating an experience, a value, or similar, related to the cultural heritage. Challenges thus included a lack of interactivity with cultural resources, such as static exhibits and non-functional materials, which limited participants' ability to translate inspiration into practical game design elements.

As highlighted above in the Hilversum case, a critical element across the cultural hubs CGJs is the possible tensions between the preservation and innovation of cultural heritage and, more tangibly, how cultural heritage is expressed in game designs, whether the connections are easily identified or more thematic, reflective, and entangled.

To improve future CGJs and their outcomes: games through/for culture, the CGJ should result in playable prototypes, as emphasised through the analyses of all games through/for culture created in CGJ 1-6 across the three QH Cultural Hubs. While prototypes are not polished or finished games, they must be sufficiently developed to facilitate meaningful gameplay and gameworlds inviting gameplayers to directly interact with and experience cultural heritage (games through culture) or cultural citizenship (games for culture). However, many games created in CGJ 1-6 struggle to meaningfully incorporate the four core categories - culture, games, values, and citizenship - into coherent and interactive games through/for culture. Playable prototypes can be described as containing game mechanics, game aesthetics, game narratives, gameplay, and game design.

Developing these core game elements should directly connect with and be crafted from cultural heritage or cultural/societal themes and issues, integrating EU values. Notably, games through/for culture should be developed through iterative cycles of conceptualisation, testing, feedback, and redesign or refinement of these categories and elements. This process enables participants to identify and address gameplay and gameworld issues early on concerning integrating cultural heritage or citizenship, ensuring stronger connections to cultural heritage/citizenship and European values. Consequently, the final CGJ Kit must facilitate youths' deliberate culture-making practices by creating value-sensitive cultural heritage/citizenship gameplay, gameworlds, game systems, game narratives, and game aesthetics. It also enables youths' processual and iterative game-making process to engage values, cultural heritage, and citizenship to create a playable prototype in the form of a game through/for culture.

Furthermore, it is crucial to establish clear goals and outcomes for game development through well-defined game design materials and effective game jam facilitation (i.e., the CGJ Kit). By guiding participants in cultural game design, the CGJ Kit ensures that the created games are both playable and culturally purposeful, providing meaningful gameplay and gameworlds concerning value-sensitive cultural heritage/citizenship. Emphasising the incorporation of locally relevant cultural themes and materials - such as tangible/intangible cultural heritage, cultural history, cultural themes, or social issues - enhances participant engagement and enables them to connect with the content both personally and collectively, thereby deepening their understanding of cultural heritage/citizenship and the values reflected in their games through/for culture.

Games through/for culture face the challenge of balancing the complexities of game design with cultural sensitivity, values, and citizenship. Not all games through/for culture from CGJ 1-6 simultaneously demonstrate a robust integration of all four core categories (games, values, culture, and citizenship). Furthermore, many games struggle to balance playful elements with serious cultural reflections, often resulting in gameplay experiences that either feel unoriginal or lack clear cultural connections. To address this, a variety of methods targeting these categories should be incorporated to create compelling cultural gameplay experiences and interactions, as well as ensure that the cultural heritage material or cultural citizenship themes are meaningfully integrated into the game. Facilitating and scaffolding cultural game-making through a CGJ Kit that targets either the creation of games through culture or games for culture ensures participants can create culturally more profound and more value-sensitive games.

Finally, implementing debrief sessions or feedback loops in the CGJ is essential for iterative and processual game development through/for culture. The CGJ Kit should include mandatory feedback opportunities such as the Expert Council, Playtesting, or the EXPO. Such feedback and discussions offer valuable insights into participants' processes and experiences, enabling adjustments to the game based on feedback.

From the activities and research in EPIC-WE, particularly the cross-hub thematic analysis of all data from CGJ 1-6 (T2.4), it is consistently noted that documentation should be integrated into the workflow to become a seamless part of the game design process. This integration allows participants to reflect on their progress without disrupting their creative flow. Many participants previously found documenting their work on digital platforms burdensome during the initial round of CGJ interventions. However, the value of documentation becomes evident when it is woven into key activities - such as expert feedback sessions, playtesting, or pitching the game concept to audiences. Simple, structured documentation prompts, like "What is the most significant insight from expert feedback?" or "What challenges are we addressing?" can be included in activities and encourage teams to reflect without adding unnecessary complexity. Furthermore, visual tools such as storyboards or sketching can replace lengthy written reports, and documentation can be shared as a collaborative group task rather than the responsibility of a single individual. The CGJ Kit is iterated to address these insights, especially regarding its Game Logs 1-4 and its Log & Pitch transition tool.

Facilitating deeper engagement with cultural heritage collections and cultural/social themes is vital for ensuring their meaningful integration of the core categories of culture, citizenship, and values into game designs. This is one of the main functions of the CGJ Kit. Multiple teams encountered challenges when incorporating cultural heritage or cultural/social themes into their games. To ensure these elements are not superficially engaged and integrated, the CGJ Kit should be developed to deliberately target and scaffold the creation of games through culture (cultural heritage game-making) and games for culture (cultural citizenship game-making). Here, immersive experiences, such as visits to cultural sites or interactive sessions with museum exhibits, can provide inspiration and context for integrating cultural heritage, themes, and EU values. Pre-jam visits to cultural sites and sessions with experts, such as cultural historians or curators, can offer participants guidance to transform cultural insights into game mechanics or narratives. During the CGJ, continuous access to professionals in culture and games helps maintain this connection throughout the event, which should also be part of the practical organisation of a CGJ (see D3.2 Protocol 4).

Overall, game-making as culture-making is supported by the dual CGJ Kit format of distinguishing between Cultural Game Jams resulting in either games through culture (cultural heritage-driven CGJs) or games for culture (cultural citizenship-driven CGJs). This necessitates redesigning the CGJ Kit developed from the D3.1 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit into two distinctive approaches or CGJ Kits that target and scaffold these two CGJ types. The implications for the final CGJ Kit – developed based on the D3.2 Protocol 2 – is further detailed in the following section.

The Heritage-focused Games through Culture Kit

05

5. The Heritage-focused Games through Culture Kit

5.1 Results and Insights from CGJ 1-6: Games through Culture

In the thematic cross-hub analyses (T2.4), a key insight is the significant integration of cultural heritage collections and materials and, furthermore, how the cultural heritage dimension is applied and utilised to create games through culture. In the initial six CGJs, participants often encountered challenges effectively incorporating abstract cultural themes into their game designs, as outlined in the thematic analysis. To address this, offering immersive experiences such as museum visits, site tours, and expert guidance can provide valuable context and inspiration. This enables participants to link cultural heritage directly to gameplay mechanics, narratives, aesthetics, and design, ensuring that these elements are not superficial additions but fundamental components that facilitate the team's release of their game through culture.

To enhance the integration of tangible/intangible cultural heritage in game design, different opportunities have emerged from the T2.4 analyses, such as arranging pre-jam visits to cultural heritage sites or interactive museum sessions and encouraging hands-on exploration of cultural heritage. Provide specific prompts, such as asking how cultural heritage artefacts could inspire gameplay and gameworld interactions and experiences. Throughout the CGJ, include cultural historians, curators, or subject-matter experts as mentors to guide participants in engaging cultural heritage as game-making material towards their delivery of a game through culture. This ensures cultural heritage facilitation is available at all stages, not just at the beginning. Additionally, encourage participants to prototype small gameplay elements of cultural heritage mechanics, narratives, or aesthetics that directly engage and integrate tangible cultural heritage and intangible cultural values.

Furthermore, it is emphasised that designing a CGJ Kit for games through culture that strikes a balance between structured guidance and opportunities for self-directed exploration ensures that participants feel supported while remaining connected to the cultural heritage materials and site. The thematic analyses revealed that participants valued using cultural heritage sites, such as art museums, digital archives, or cultural landmarks, which stimulated creativity and engagement with the cultural heritage materials and themes. However, frequent changes in location or excessively open-ended processes and spaces led to feelings of disorientation and confusion, hindering the deeper connections between cultural heritage and the development of games through culture.

Reviewing the games created from the initial six CGJs (based on the analysis of all games through/for culture in T2.4 and T4.3) – and drawing upon hub reflections and cross-hub evaluations (T4.1) and feedback workshops (T3.4) – the integration of cultural heritage and European values is rarely the core focus. Generally, these elements tend to be emphasised differently; one tends to be prioritised over the other. Therefore, the CGJ Kit for games through culture must utilise cultural heritage as both a material and a medium for game development and methods for reconfiguring, transmitting, or emphasising cultural heritage features, qualities, or values. This also corresponds to and influences the CGJ Kit as a heritage-driven or citizenship-driven approach. The heritage-driven CGJ Kit targeting the creation of games through culture, profoundly highlights the cultural heritage domain and is intricately related to game-making deeply embedded within cultural heritage sites and collections. In contrast, the citizenship-driven approach invites youth to engage in culture- and value-sensitive citizenship through creating games for culture (e.g. games engaging societal issues or cultural themes, belonging, or identities).

Utilising cultural heritage as engaging and empowering game-making material within the CGJs and through the CGJ Kit enhances participant involvement and creates more engaging and meaningful cultural gameplay and gameworld interactions and experiences. Redesigning the CGJ Kit to target cultural heritage as game-making material and creating games through culture cultivates personal and collective connections to cultural heritage, promoting a deeper appreciation and reflection on the values and contexts presented.

To address this, games through culture CGJs must ensure that cultural heritage and European values are seamlessly integrated into the CGJ experience through the CGJ Kit. This approach prevents games from becoming detached from the dimensions of cultural heritage and European values. Facilitation and scaffolding of cultural heritage through the CGJ Kit for games through culture is vital for creating informed cultural heritage gameplay, gameworlds, and narratives.

5.2 The CGJ Kit for Games through Culture

In more detail, the CGJ Kit for **games through culture** will directly engage and transform the initial CGJ Kit in the following ways:

A. EPIC-WE Cultural Heritage Game Jam Phases

Each phase of the **Cultural Game Jam Process Model** will be redesigned to specifically engage the intersection of tangible cultural heritage materials and intangible European values to guide participants in creating games through culture.

Experience Phase

- Focuses on **cultural exploration** of tangible cultural heritage, encouraging participants to engage with it as game-making material.
- Uses targeted game-making and culture-making methods to inspire game concepts through cultural heritage.

Play Phase

- Centres on **playful experimentation** with cultural heritage gameplay experiences, interactions, mechanics, aesthetics, and narratives.
- Uses methods focused on experimenting with cultural heritage and European values as game-making material.

Imagine Phase

- Involves **refining and materialising game ideas** into tangible games through culture prototypes.
- Uses developed methods that facilitate the playtesting of cultural heritage gameplay and gameworlds to ensure gameplayers' meaningful cultural heritage interactions and experiences.

Create Phase

- Participants produce a playable game through culture for gameplayers to experience and engage with the intersection of cultural heritage and European values through the medium of gameplay and gameworld culture.

B. EPIC-WE Cultural Heritage Dimensions: Cultural Heritage World and Empowerment

Two overarching dimensions, **World** and **Empowerment (W-E)**, run through all phases of the CGJ:

World Dimension:

- Focuses on experience of and interaction with cultural heritage sites, environments, collections, and materials.

Empowerment Dimension:

- Encourages youth to engage with cultural heritage through empowered participation, enabling them to become co-creators of cultural heritage by creating games through culture.

C. EPIC-WE Cultural Heritage Transition Tools

To facilitate the smooth transition between phases, the CGJ Kit for games through culture introduces four Cultural Heritage Transition Tools, one for each phase:

Ideation Wheel:

- Helps participants experience and generate multiple ideas that engage cultural heritage and European values as game-making materials.

Expert Council:

- Provides youth with targeted feedback on using cultural heritage and European values from experts and professionals in games and culture.

Playtest:

- The construction of cultural heritage mock-ups or prototypes that enable participants to test and adjust their games through culture based on playtesting of the cultural heritage and European values experiences and interactions.

Log & Pitch:

- Prepares teams to showcase their game through culture to audiences at the final EXPO and publish it at the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#).

D. EPIC-WE Core Cultural Heritage Categories: Culture, Values and Games

The CGJ Kit for games through culture and its methods are structured around three of the four core categories: Cultural heritage, European values, and games through culture.

During the Spring of 2025, the CGJ Kit for games through culture will be developed and delivered. The CGJ Kit will be based on this final D3.2 Protocol 2 and a redesign of the CGJ Kit developed from the initial D3.1 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit. The CGJ Kit for games through culture will focus on utilising cultural heritage as game-making material and creating games through culture.

The Citizenship- focused Games for Culture Kit

06

6. The Citizenship-focused Games for Culture Kit

6.1 Results and Insights from CGJ 1-6: Games for Culture

The cross-analysis (T4.3 and T2.4) of the 54 games created through/for culture during CGJ 1-6 shows that the cultural citizenship dimension resonates with clear goals and outcomes, cultural/societal themes, problems, and scenarios, and, importantly, balances the complexities of designing between citizenship, values, and games.

By addressing cultural and societal themes, issues, identities, and voices, games for culture have the potential to empower youth citizenship through facilitating reflections and discussions (in the form of game-making) around inclusion, diversity, belonging, and identities in culture and society. Youth participants across the three QH Cultural Hubs and CGJ 1-6 emphasised the potential of games for culture to mediate cultural and societal themes, issues, and values. However, challenges in effectively integrating cultural insights into games for culture. There was a consensus on the importance of value-sensitive facilitation and resources that connect cultural themes and issues with practical game design processes. Curated cultural themes and issues (integrating European values) and targeted games for culture CGJ could help address these gaps, fostering more profound engagement and empowerment with cultural/societal themes across diverse settings. This shared necessity for structured, yet adaptable resources and facilitation highlights the global relevance of tailored support in CGJs. In creating games for culture, the perspective of relational aesthetics, as discussed at the second CGJ in Aarhus, becomes significant – along with facilitating spaces and processes for empowered youth citizenship – to drive cultural and societal engagement.

As emphasised in the thematic analysis (T2.4), the cultural citizenship dimension was both significant and sometimes underdeveloped in the delivery and testing of the local CGJs. One example is the Óbidos CGJs, where the structural and organisational dynamics and developments led to power asymmetries through the lack of youth participation and integration in developing and shaping the CGJs, their facilitation, themes, and agendas. Though they were actively engaged during the CGJs, they thus became end-users instead of epistemic and practical partners in planning and evaluating the events.

However, the central pillar of games for culture is youth citizenship. CGJs for culture should empower young citizens to take ownership of cultural innovation, engage in cultural and societal themes and issues, and position themselves as co-creators of European culture and society. Through creating games for culture, participants are encouraged to explore their cultural identities, experiment with creative ideas, and develop game prototypes that reflect their personal and collective voices and identities. This hands-on engagement with European values and cultural/societal themes and issues can foster a more profound sense of cultural belonging, agency, and empowerment, enabling youth to shape shared cultural narratives and futures actively. Ultimately, games for culture within CGJs serve as a transformative method, promoting cultural sensitivity, awareness, and active and engaged citizenship, while providing a dynamic CGJ format for empowered dialogues and cultural transformation through creating games for culture.

6.2 The Games for Culture Kit

In more detail, the CGJ Kit for **games through culture** will directly engage and transform the initial CGJ Kit in the following ways:

A. EPIC-WE Cultural Citizenship Game Jam Phases

Each phase of the **Cultural Game Jam Process Model** will be redesigned to specifically engage the intersection of empowered citizenship in culture and society with European values to guide participants in creating games for culture.

Experience Phase

- Focuses on cultural exploration of cultural/societal themes and issues, encouraging participants to engage with these through game-making processes.
- Uses targeted game-making and culture-making methods to inspire game concepts for culture, society, and citizenship.

Play Phase

- Centres on **playful experimentation** with cultural heritage gameplay experiences, interactions, mechanics, aesthetics, and narratives.
- Uses methods that are focused on experimenting with cultural themes and issues, societal challenges, and European values as game-making material.

Imagine Phase

- Involves **refining and materialising cultural/societal game ideas** into tangible games for culture prototypes.
- Uses developed methods that facilitate the playtesting of cultural/societal gameplay and gameworlds to ensure gameplayers' meaningful citizenship interactions and experiences.

Create Phase

- Participants produce a playable game for culture for gameplayers to experience and engage with the intersection of citizenship, cultural-social themes and issues, and European values through the medium of gameplay and gameworld culture.

B. EPIC-WE Cultural Citizenship Dimensions: Cultural Heritage World and Empowerment

Two overarching dimensions, **World** and **Empowerment (W-E)**, run through all phases of the CGJ:

World Dimension:

- Focuses on materialisation of and interaction with cultural citizenship, identities, diversity, voices, and values.

Empowerment Dimension:

- Encourages youth to engage with/in cultural citizenship through empowered participation, enabling them to become co-creators of culture and society through creating games for culture.

C. EPIC-WE Cultural Citizenship Transition Tools

To facilitate the smooth transition between phases, the CGJ Kit for games for culture introduces four **Cultural Citizenship Transition Tools**, one for each phase:

Ideation Wheel:

- Helps participants experience and generate multiple ideas that engage cultural citizenship and European values as game-making approaches to cultural/societal themes and issues.

Expert Council:

- Provides youth with targeted feedback on their engagement with cultural/societal themes and issues and European values from experts and professionals in games and culture.

Playtest:

- The construction of cultural citizenship mock-ups or prototypes that enable participants to test and adjust their games for culture based on playtesting of the cultural/societal themes or issues, and the European values that gameplayers interact with and experience.

Log & Pitch:

- Prepares teams to showcase their game for culture to audiences at the final EXPO and publish it at the [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#).

D. EPIC-WE Core Cultural Citizenship Categories: Culture, values and Games

The CGJ Kit for games for culture and its methods are structured around three of the four core categories: Cultural citizenship, European values, and games for culture.

The CGJ Kit for games for culture will be developed and delivered in the spring of 2025. It will be based on this final D3.2 Protocol 2 and a redesign of the CGJ Kit developed from the initial D3.1 Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit. The CGJ Kit for games for culture will focus on empowering cultural citizenship through game-making with cultural/societal themes and issues and creating games for culture.

Conclusion

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7. Conclusion

The EPIC-WE project demonstrates how cultural game jams (CGJs) can serve as innovative and transformative events for fostering cultural engagement, participatory citizenship, and cultural-creative game-making. Through the iterative development and refinement of the Cultural Game Jam Kit (CGJ Kit), the project has established a structured yet adaptable kit that empowers young people to create **games through culture** and **games for culture**. The CGJs have facilitated new forms of cultural participation, engagement, and empowerment by integrating cultural heritage, citizenship, and values into game-making processes.

The findings from the first six CGJs highlight several core achievements of the project:

Empowered Participation and Co-Creation:

The CGJs have positioned game-making as a meaningful form of culture-making, enabling youth to engage as active contributors to and partners in cultural innovation and transformation. Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) have strengthened participatory and democratic dynamics, ensuring that young people are involved in both the organisation and running of CGJs.

Games as Cultural and Civic Engagement Tools:

The dual focus on *games through culture* (leveraging cultural heritage as game-making material) and *games for culture* (exploring cultural and societal themes through game-making) has demonstrated the potential of combining culture and games.

A Scalable and Adaptable CGJ Kit:

The project has developed and validated three compositions of the CGJ Kit - **Focused, Flexible, and Freeform** - allowing for adaptable applications in different contexts. This approach balances structure with creative autonomy, ensuring that CGJs remain accessible and responsive to diverse cultural settings, institutional partners, and participant backgrounds.

Integration of Cultural Heritage and Creative Industries:

The collaboration between cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and higher education has enriched the CGJ process, reinforcing the role of cultural facilitators, game designers, and academics in co-developing meaningful and reflective game-making experiences with/in cultural heritage.

Recommendations for Future Research and Practical Implementation

Building on these insights, the following recommendations can guide future iterations of CGJs and enhance their continued impact:

1 Strengthen Youth Participation and Co-Design

Expanding the role of YABs in shaping CGJ themes, structuring activities, and contributing to facilitation will further reinforce the project's commitment to youth empowerment.

2 Enhance Inclusivity and Accessibility

Providing pre-CGJ preparation materials, structured mentorship, and interdisciplinary team formations will help bridge experience gaps and ensure equitable participation, particularly for those less familiar with game jam methodologies.

3 Embed Reflection and Documentation into CGJs

Refining documentation processes through integrated reflection activities, structured feedback loops, and adaptable log formats will allow participants to capture their creative and cultural insights more effectively.

4 Strengthen Cross-Sectoral Collaboration

Continued engagement between cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth citizens will ensure that CGJs remain embedded in a wider Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, brought to life in the QH cultural Hubs, enhancing the culture, citizenship, values, and game dimensions of game-making.

5 Expand and Localise CGJ Applications

Future initiatives should test the adaptability of the CGJ Kit across a broader range of cultural heritage contexts, ensuring that local, glocal, and sectoral dimensions are fully integrated into the methodology.

The EPIC-WE project has demonstrated that cultural game jams can serve as empowering formats and engaging sites for cultural heritage engagement, transformation, and participatory citizenship. By enabling youth to actively engage and shape cultural heritage and citizenship through their creation of games through/for culture, the CGJs showcase how empowered participation in cultural worlds and environments might look and be practiced.

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